

Managing the Implementation of the Senior High School Alternative Learning System (ALS) Program: Perspective of Mobile Teachers

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A Thesis Presented to the Graduate Education Faculty
St. Mary's College of Tagum, Inc.,
Tagum City, Davao de Norte

In Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the Degree
Master of Arts in Education major in
Educational Management

APPROVAL SHEET

This thesis titled, “**MANAGING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL ALTERNATIVE LEARNING SYSTEM (ALS) PROGRAM: PERSPECTIVE OF MOBILE TEACHERS,**” prepared and submitted by **NERISSA C. VILLABER**, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree, **Master of Arts in Education major in Educational Management**, has been examined and hereby recommended for approval and acceptance.

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ABSTRACT

This phenomenological study aimed to explore the implementation of the ALS Senior High School program in Tagum City, Davao del Norte. Also, this study aimed to discover the lived experiences, challenges, coping strategies, and insights of ALS mobile teachers in managing the implementation of the ALS senior high school program. This study was participated by the 10 ALS mobile teachers from the Schools Division of Tagum City, Davao del Norte. These participants were selected through purposive sampling and selection criteria. More so, all the ALS mobile teachers participated in in-depth interviews and focus group discussions. After a thorough analysis of the responses of the participants, the following themes emerged: difficulties and adjustments in teaching ALS – SHS; unavailability of the curriculum guide and LIS intended for ALS – SHS; difficulties in producing modules and teaching materials; lack of teachers for ALS – SHS; asking and receiving assistance from stakeholders; researching and studying; using other strategies to solve problems; managing time; positive outlooks of becoming an ALS – SHS Mobile Teacher; professional growth and personal gains; provision of additional budget, training, and teachers for ALS – SHS program; continue learning as a teacher in ALS – SHS; assessment and monitoring of the ALS – SHS Program; and designing of specific curriculum for ALS – SHS. Finally, it is understood that the results of this study could be a basis for the improvement of ALS-SHS implementation.

Keywords:- Educational Management, ALS Senior High School, ALS Mobile Teachers, ALS Learners, Phenomenology, Davao Del Norte

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This thesis reached its completion through the most genuine individuals I worked with. To say that I was fortunate to meet them during the process is an understatement. They were the wisdom that I asked from the heavens.

To my thesis adviser, Dr. Mervin G. Salmon, I am grateful you enlightened me, a juvenile researcher, who traveled on this study in the pursuit of development. The knowledge you shared and the passion you passed on will forever be kept and cultivated.

To the Dean of Graduate School, Dr. Perla C. Padro, thank you for the constant supervision and relentless reminder of my duty as a researcher, with the desire for honest work. Your support also persuaded me to carry on.

To the data analyst and editor, Jinedeth T. Cemin, LPT, MAEd, thank you so much for diligently analyzing the data results from the interview. The analyzed data was necessary for achieving the purpose of this study.

To the validators: Dr. Maria Lalaine P. Chieng, Dr. Celso Casamayor, and Dr. Geraldine Canlas thank you for validating my interview guide questions that served as tools I used in collecting the experiences of my participants that are extremely essential to the study.

To the 10 participants from the Schools of Tagum City, Davao del Norte, thank you for sharing your invaluable experiences and realizations. Your honest responses to the different guide questions supplied vital information, needed in this research.

To the panel members led by Dr. Perla C. Padro with the members, namely: Dr. Ryan A. Jancinal, Dr. Maria Lalaine P. Chieng, Dr. Celso G. Casamayor Jr., and Dr. Lucena O. Asidoy, thank you so much for giving me constructive and positive feedback. Your remarks guaranteed me that my hard work and restless nights did not go to waste.

To the SMCTI - Research Ethics Committee (REC), thank you for patiently checking my manuscript and giving me various comments and suggestions for the improvement of my study, ensuring that it conformed to the required standards.

To the Schools Division Superintendent of DepEd Tagum City Division, thank you for approving the conduct of this study. Without your authorization, this study would not be feasible.

To my colleagues, friends, and family, you have witnessed my steady and earnest effort, and my devoted and painstaking work to accomplish this undertaking. You lend assistance in any way possible, thank you.

Above all, I praise my Lord and Savior Jesus Christ for his love that led me to my life's victories. Without the love at the cross, I would not understand the value of living and as to why I should continue to battle for the good even to conduct a study like this.

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CHAPTER ONE INTRODUCTION

In the lives of Filipinos, education is one of the most significant accomplishments one can make. Higher education opens doors to opportunities that will give them a promising future and help them escape their current situation once and for all. However, for a variety of reasons, many Filipinos are unable to enroll in and finish formal basic education. Some students leave school early, while others reside in areas without any schools. The Alternative Learning System (ALS) was formed by the government to ensure that all Filipinos have access to finish basic education in a setting that is suited to their conditions and requirements because everyone is entitled to free basic education.

In Indonesia, the Indonesian Research and Development Center found that just seven schools out of 8,306 were at the country's senior high school level. Nonetheless, it struggled to demonstrate educational opportunities for students. As a result, senior high school implementers encountered problems in enhancing and sustaining the program so that it will cater to more out-of-school youth and adults before they can enroll in tertiary education (Ingilinar, 2019). In Laos, the Education ministry encourages the senior high school coordinators to intensify the program so that out-of-school students will continually and smoothly pursue their high school years before pursuing their bachelor's courses. However, the Education Ministry and the coordinators in senior high schools are complaining since they received inconsistent support from the government (Caimar, 2018). In India, senior high school teachers faced different issues in implementing the program since some of the students are drop out of school because of personal problems. It has been reported in a government study that the dropout rate at senior high school levels is more than 17%, compared to 1.8% and 1.5%, respectively, at the upper-primary (grades VI to VIII) and elementary levels (ABP New Bureau, 2021).

Meanwhile, in the Philippines, according to recent statistics, around 3.7 million youths aged 16-24 and 3.1 million young adults aged 25-30 in the Philippines did not complete junior high or senior high school and are now out of school. In response to these recent findings, the Department of Education launched the Alternative Learning System - Senior high school in 2019. ALS implementers struggled in implementing the program when ALS senior high schools started in some regions in the Philippines. Additionally, the lack of resources, budget, and workforce are the main problems faced by mobile teachers when ALS was piloted in different regions in the Philippines. Mobile teachers could not smoothly implement the program in the National Capital Region because ALS funding has stayed at less than one percent of the total community basic education budget since its inception (The Philippine News Agency, 2021).

In the Department of Education - Tagum City Division, the implementation of ALS senior high school has run into many difficulties, notably for mobile teachers. They oversee putting the curriculum to work. Mobile teachers lack resources and knowledge of the Senior High School curriculum. Also, mobile teachers experience problems in the implementation because they do not have enough workforce to cater to around 262 learners enrolled in the program. Additionally, mobile teachers had to cope with changes in rules and operational processes, which necessitated the close monitoring of school administrators and supervisors daily. Aside from that, there was insufficient training and seminars accessible to ALS senior high school teachers.

From the problem mentioned above, it was determined that there was an urgent need for an academic report on this problem. There are studies related to ALS such as the study of Abad and Galleto (2020) entitled, "Alternative Learning System Program's Implementation Landscape of a Division in The Philippines" and the study of Adajar, Caingcoy, and Pacursa (2021) entitled "Effectiveness of the Alternative Learning System Informal Education Project and the Transfer of Life Skills among ALS Teachers: A Case Study." These investigations varied from this phenomenological research because they dealt with the implementation of ALS Senior High School in Tagum City.

Certainly, as the researcher, I recognized the significance of undertaking this phenomenological study considering the aforementioned issues. This study is an excellent opportunity to become a researched-based solution to ALS problems, specifically in ALS senior high school implementation. Consequently, every academic research aims to help the community's different sectors, particularly the education sector. Simply this study will create social awareness in society and knowledge to people on how mobile teachers faced different complexities in managing the ALS senior high school.

Thus, this study could be a great research reference for society in aiding mobile teachers to improve their delivery of the ALS senior high school program. With that, society could benefit from the collaborative effort they will be doing, as it will expand the reach of the ALS program. Lastly, the output of this study will be submitted to the international, national, and local presentations and I will be joining research forums and conferences to share the result of my study to the community and the society.

A. Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this phenomenological research was to investigate and understand the different experiences of 10 mobile teachers as they manage the implementation of the Alternative Learning System - Senior High School in the Division of Tagum City. Additionally, this research intends to recognize the efforts of mobile teachers in managing the ALS senior high school by maximizing their goals and strategies to completely implement the program in the Tagum City Division.

At this stage in the research, mobile teachers in the Alternative Learning System are generally defined as individuals who are responsible for managing the implementation of the Alternative Learning System - Senior High School program in the Division of Tagum, Davao del Norte.

B. Research Questions

- What are the lived experiences of mobile teachers in managing the implementation of ALS senior high school?
- How do mobile teachers cope with the challenges encountered in ALS senior high school implementation?
- What insights can be drawn from the experiences of mobile teachers in the implementation of ALS senior high school?

C. Theoretical Lens

This study is gleaned through the Diffusion Theory of Everett M. Rogers (1962). As cited by Singhal (2019), Rogers' Diffusion Theory examines how teachers as managers combine new ideas. Rogers defines how new knowledge is learned, implemented, and maintained. Also, he developed an innovation-decision model to describe this process: Knowledge, Persuasion, Decision, Implementation, and Confirmation as the five steps of the process. These stages are the basis to understand how professional development helped teacher-managers achieve new skills and knowledge. Researchers studied implementation, particularly re-invention. Moreover, Rogers emphasized that collaboration with other teacher managers linking the innovation to a bigger purpose is an opportunity for teacher managers to effectively practice management.

The abovementioned theory was used to explore the struggles of mobile teachers in creating collaborative efforts to effectively manage the implementation of ALS senior high school. Mobile teachers in ALS encountered difficulties in integrating their professional education knowledge to re-invent effective leadership skills in implementing the ALS-Senior High School Program. They faced different struggles in managing the implementation of ALS-SHS since they are busy with their other commitments as being on the front line in ALS. Mobile teachers struggled to manage the ALS-SHS because it is a newly launched program in DepEd. As an effect, mobile teachers are challenged to provide a shared leadership that would effectively support the implementation of ALS-SHS. Moreover, mobile teachers are challenged to learn new management strategies suitable for the implementation of ALS-SHS. Also, mobile teachers are having difficulties incorporating their abilities and skills to make effective supervision since most of them are originally teaching at the ALS elementary level or ALS junior high school. Thus, mobile teachers are challenged to ask for some guidance from the Formal Education-SHS to fully acquire knowledge on the implementation of the program.

In addition, this study is also supported by the Scientific Management Theory of Frederick Taylor (1911). The goal of this theory is to raise individual productivity to boost output and implementation within an organization. Scientific management philosophy advocates for standards, expertise, ability-based assignment, intensive training, and monitoring. Using these methods is the only way to achieve efficiency and productivity in a program. The goal of this management philosophy is to discover the most efficient method for accomplishing a certain activity. Several successful programs have been built on this approach, which focuses on workplace efficiency, training, and collaboration.

The abovementioned theory points out that mobile teachers struggled to provide comprehensive shared leadership since they still need to undertake necessary training and workshop on how to implement the academic tracks in senior high school. Mobile teachers also encountered problems in teaching the different academic tracks in ALS-SHS since they do not have the facilities, materials, and services that could efficiently implement the program. As a result, mobile teachers are still needed to ask permission from the school administrators of formal education to use the facilities and materials of senior high school-formal education. Also, mobile teachers allotted so much time to studying the topics in ALS senior high school because sometimes they are not so familiar with the topics aligned with the SHS curriculum. With that, mobile teachers decrease their productivity to effectively implement the program.

Lastly, this study is supported by Republic Act No. 11510, commonly referred to as the Alternative Learning System Act, which aims to provide adequate, responsive, and quality recognition and support to the basic educational needs of out-of-school children in special circumstances and adults, including indigenous peoples (IPs). The legislation strengthens and expands the ALS program to give more chances for basic and functional literacy and life skills development, as well as an equivalent path to basic education completion. It promotes lifelong learning opportunities for out-of-school children in unique circumstances and adult learners, including indigenous people, as part of the ALS K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum (The Philippine News Agency, 2019).

The abovementioned law firmly emphasizes that mobile teachers deliver quality education to out-of-school children and adults, including indigenous people. Also, mobile teachers in ALS promote lifelong learning that allows the out-of-school youth and adults to enroll in ALS K to 12 programs. With this, the ALS program expands its reach to eradicate illiteracy in its area. However, mobile teachers have their own set of challenges in the implementation of the ALS-SHS program, including difficulties in enrolling students, absenteeism, bad thoughts from families and even community leaders regarding ALS, and inadequate funding to support the program. Moreover, mobile teachers struggled to find linkages and partnerships from different stakeholders to fully implement their plans and policies in helping the least, the lost, and the last.

D. Scope and Limitation of the Study

This phenomenological research focused on 10 mobile teachers assigned to supervise the Alternative Learning System Senior High implementation in the Tagum City Division. Thus, three (3) participants participated in In-Depth Interviews (IDI), and seven (7) participants participated in a Focus Group Discussion (FGD), from which I extracted the needed data for this study. The study was conducted during the academic year 2021–2022, from August to December 2022.

Additionally, the study did not include mobile educators who were not given the responsibility of overseeing the implementation of the Senior High School Alternative Learning System. Because data were only gathered from a particular group of participants, this study did not specifically highlight all mobile teachers employed by the Department of Education. The findings of this study should not be interpreted as a comprehensive representation of the Alternative Learning System - Department of Education.

E. Importance of the Study

The importance of this phenomenological study can be attributed to the following people and entities:

For **mobile teachers in ALS senior high school**, this study may be an excellent opportunity to capacitate their management abilities to manage the implementation of the Alternative Learning System – Senior High School and implementation of other ALS programs. This study will be an outstanding chance for them to participate in more collective endeavors to realize their ALS senior high school implementation plans. Also, this study will help them understand that they play an essential part in the achievement of ALS – Senior High School as they provide managerial supervision. Moreover, this study may improve their strategic and management plans to identify the challenges during ALS senior high school implementation.

For the **ALS learners**, as the immediate beneficiaries of the implementation of ALS senior high school, this study will give them an idea of the underlying challenges that their mobile teachers are experiencing in terms of the execution of the ALS senior high school course. With that, they will be able to support the success of the implementation of ALS senior high school.

For the **DepEd Officials**, this study will serve as the source for exploring involvement projects, plans, and training that would improve mobile teachers' strategic plans to implement the ALS senior high school program fully. Also, the Department of Education officials may prioritize the demands and difficulties of mobile teachers in the implementation of the ALS senior high school program. Also, the DepEd officials may provide effective and helpful assistance to improve the delivery of the Alternative Learning System – Senior High School Program.

Lastly, for **future and other researchers**, this study will serve as their reference especially if they will study related topics on ALS. Also, this study will help them create additional academic studies on different problems of the Alternative Learning System. Moreover, this study will help them entirely comprehend how mobile teachers faced problems implementing various programs in the Alternative Learning System.

F. Definition of Terms

A conceptual and operational explanation of important terms used in this study is provided below to give a higher level of quality and a better comprehension of the context of this research study.

➤ *Senior High School.*

This is defined as a high school that offers the last years of secondary education, usually grades 11 and 12 (Meriam Webster Dictionary, 2021). As utilized in this study, this refers to the last two (2) years of education in high school, particularly in grades 11 and 12 offered by the Alternative Learning System to the out-of-school youth and adults, wherein they are required to go through a core curriculum and subjects under a track of their choice before enrolling in tertiary education.

➤ *Mobile Teachers.*

This refers to trained teachers who live amongst the people in distant barangays to conduct the Basic Literacy Program (BLP) for illiterate, out-of-school youth and adults who are eager to study the fundamentals of literacy, and the Accreditation and Equivalency Program (a continuing education) for persons who left the formal school system or do not have access to classrooms (DepEd Region XI, 2019). As utilized in this study, this refers to the public-school teachers designated to manage the implementation of the Alternative Learning System - Senior High School Program in the Division of Tagum City.

G. Organization of the Study

This study was planned and structured in such a way that it is easily identifiable and comprehensible to the readers. The following is a detailed explanation and discussion of the study's organization:

- *Chapter 1* introduces the phenomenon of the study. The first chapter includes the purpose of this study and the research questions that were used as a guide to explore the phenomenon. I have a thorough understanding of the phenomena and the data collection process. Several significant concepts in this research are defined operationally and technically in the definition of terms. This chapter also defines the study's scope and limitations. Additionally, a theoretical lens is herein discussed in this chapter.
- *Chapter 2* presents a review of related literature in which essential concepts, findings, and ideas, as well as understandings of the subject, are featured in this study from research sourced from various books, internet articles, publications, and other media to comprehensively discuss and present the phenomenon being showcased in this research paper.
- *Chapter 3* explains the research design, the research participants, the researcher's role, data sources, data collection, and data analysis. This chapter also explains the four components of dependability of the study: credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability, and ends with an assessment of the study's ethical considerations.
- *Chapter 4* shows the study's results utilizing the ideas acquired from the IDI and FGD interviews. It contains a table of themes, main key concepts, and a summary of conclusions generated after the interview record has been reviewed and analyzed.
- *Chapter 5* analyzes and summarizes the findings of this phenomenological investigation. This chapter extracts the significant problems and conclusions from this investigation, along with fundamentals and supporting statements from a variety of sources. The implications for teaching practice, recommendations for further research, and concluding remarks are also presented in this chapter about participants' perceptions and experiences with this research project.

CHAPTER TWO

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This section includes some pertinent literature and studies that directly relate to the study, as well as the background and framework for the investigation. The articles included in this chapter were taken from a range of reputable authors' books, journals, and other secondary sources.

A. Alternative Learning System

The Philippine Department of Education created the Alternative Learning System (ALS), a parallel educational program that offers a respectable substitute for conventional education (Yu, 2018 as cited in Salendab & Cogo, 2022). The Department of Education's Alternative Learning System now makes it possible for out-of-school kids, people who aren't readers, working Filipinos, and even the elderly, who were previously unable to earn a high school diploma, to do so (Tiongco, 2019).

ALS includes informal and non-formal sources of knowledge and skills, according to the Department of Education (2019). In order to brush up on or learn new skills, primarily in elementary and secondary education, this system can be used by dropouts, out-of-school children, non-readers, working people, and even older citizens. ALS facilitators conduct lessons in students' homes, multipurpose rooms, and group learning centers. The ALS program offers its participants a straightforward second chance. But in order for people to reach their full potential, it needs to be changed frequently. Other nations facing a similar situation on a global scale may benefit from the lessons learned from the Philippines' experience with ALS.

In the study conducted by Acosta et al. (2020), one of the largest second-chance education systems in the world is found in the Philippines, which has more than a million enrolled students. Knoller (2020) explained that in the preceding decade, the Alternative Learning System, or ALS, served 5.5 million adolescent and adult learners aged 15 and older.

Moreover, the World Bank has been advising the Department of Education on how to improve its performance and proceed to a higher level. President Duterte signed Republic Act No. 11510, also known as the Alternative Learning System Act, on December 23, 2021, to guarantee that out-of-school children and adults, including indigenous peoples, receive sufficient, timely, and high-quality attention and assistance to meet their fundamental learning requirements (IPs). The Act strengthens and broadens the ALS program, giving out-of-school children, adult learners, and indigenous peoples more opportunities to complete their elementary education and gain important reading and life skills (Parrocha, 2021). It assures further that all children, particularly those from poor and conflict-affected communities, have access to comprehensive, adaptable, and appropriate alternative basic education programs outside of the traditional school system. Learners become empathetic, self-sufficient, autonomous, productive, and patriotic citizens after finishing the ALS program and completing the qualification and equivalency examinations (Ruiz et al., 2020).

Similarly, between 2016 and 2017, the number of ALS students who received assistance from the program increased by 537,666, indicating that the initiative has made significant progress toward its goal of serving 641,584 students. According to recent data, approximately 3.7 million young people between the ages of 16 and 24 and 3.1 million young adults between the ages of 25 and 30 have not completed junior high school (Sanders, 2021). Even worse, 23% of individuals between the ages of 15 and 30 are out of school (World Bank, 2018). Tinga (2020), on the other hand, stated that one out of every 10 Filipinos aged six to 24 is not enrolled in any formal schooling. Even before the crisis, the equivalent of approximately 3.6 million Filipino adolescents and teenagers had their educational opportunities hampered. According to Borela (2020), this could be due to a variety of factors such as family obligations, financial difficulties, or any number of other factors. Adolescents and adults who have not completed their formal education can earn an elementary or high school diploma through remote education through the Alternative Learning System. More importantly, according to their perspective, Alternative Learning System is viewed as a path to increased employment opportunities, despite socioeconomic or situational obstacles (Lopez-Cobar, 2022).

Consequently, ALS programs and efforts have aided in the advancement of ALS learners in a variety of ways, including educational achievement, family monthly income, employment status, and the kind and nature of their occupations (Ruiz et al., 2020). The ALS A&E program showed effectiveness in developing participants' life skills. It established that lifelong learning is most effectively accomplished outside of the traditional classroom context. The local government's support and that of other stakeholders ensured the long-term sustainability of ALS programs and project implementation. ALS's success cannot be quantified just in terms of the number of individuals who enroll, complete the course, and pass the test; rather, it must be quantified in terms of the positive effect it has on people's lives (Egcas & Garganera, 2019).

Additionally, the Philippines News Agency (2021) reported that to ensure that learners develop into caring, self-sufficient, independent, productive, and patriotic citizens, the Alternative Learning System (ALS) provides pathways across modes of learning that enable such learners to pursue additional education after completing the Alternative Learning System literacy program and passing the accreditation and certification processes. The Alternative Learning System also aimed to increase access to school and other forms of learning, as well as to achieve a greater level of literacy.

Based on DepEd Order 13, series 2019, Senior High School, which corresponds to Grades 11 and 12 in the formal educational system, was necessary (Policy Guidelines for the Implementation of the Enhanced Alternative Learning System 2.0). Its goal is to equip all ALS students with the abilities necessary for postsecondary education, self-employment, the workforce, and middle-level skills. Republic Act No. 11510 (ALS Act), which went into effect in December 2020, further supports this by stating that students who pass the A&E Test at the Elementary level are eligible to enroll in Junior High School (JHS), while students who pass the A&E Test at the JHS level are eligible to enroll in Senior High School (SHS) or certain technical vocational education and training programs run by the Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA) (Department of Education, 2021).

Also, according to Tecson (2021), moreover, 230 public high schools in Central Luzon have implemented the Alternative Learning System (ALS), with around 1,722 senior high school (SHS) students enrolling this semester. By DepEd Order 13, series 2019 (Policy Guidelines on the Implementation of Enhanced Alternative Learning System 2.0), the Department of School mandated the addition of the SHS level in the ALS program, which is like Grades 11 and 12 in the formal education system. In general, it ensures that all ALS students are equipped with the required skills and information for employment, business, and middle-level and postsecondary studies. The country's first ALS program was launched in Albay in 2019 by DepEd Region V, a division of the Department of Education. The American Learning Standards target a variety of talents, including preparation for jobs, entrepreneurship, middle-level skills, and higher education. Non-formal and informal education methodologies and tactics are being created, integrated, and used in the delivery of ALS programs, as well as in the evaluation of ALS learners' learning outcomes and competencies. The legislation does this by allowing for flexibility in the length of educational programs, the substance of educational programs, and delivery methodologies, among other things (Cabanban, 2021).

Furthermore, according to Lim (2019), the Senior High School - Alternative Learning System (ALS) is a program offered by the Department of Education (DepEd) in collaboration with several higher curriculum institutions that provide a Senior High School (SHS) education (HEIs). The ALS mobile teachers are working on the ALS Senior High School. Currently, the Department of Education (2019) is working on the curriculum for ALS SHS, the learning materials to be utilized, and the teacher training program. It is anticipated that the ALS - SHS curriculum will incorporate team teaching with formal schools that provide the SHS program, depending on which exit option the learner chooses. If they decide to continue their education after SHS, they will need to develop fundamental competencies and the specialties that they will learn at school. Should learners select TVL for employment or skills training, they must complete core topics in secondary school and skills training.

Conversely, according to Tiongco (2019), the ALS Senior High School is a new program offered by the Department of Education. It is intended to help graduates of the ALS junior high school. Numerous variables have a role in many Filipinos' incapacity to enroll in and finish formal elementary education for a variety of reasons. Certain pupils drop out of school, while others live in locations without schools. Because every Filipino is entitled to free basic education, the government developed the Senior High School-Alternative Learning System (ALS) to enable all Filipinos to gain access to and complete basic learning in a way that is adapted to their situations and needs.

Interestingly, the ALS Senior High School is a new program supported by the Department of Education that intends to assist ALS junior high school graduates in acquiring different skills and knowledge that will aid in their job search. With over a million students enrolled, the Philippines has one of the most comprehensive second-chance education programs in the world. 5.5 million adolescent and adult learners aged 15 and older have been serviced by the ALS, the Alternative Learning System. ALS is a straightforward second chance program that benefits its members. Nonetheless, it must be adjusted regularly to ensure that individuals attain their maximum potential (Acosta et al., 2020).

B. Mobile Teachers and Their Roles in Managing the ALS Program

The Alternative Learning System (ALS) programs, according to the Department of Education, Davao Region (2020), provide illiterate out-of-school children and adults who want to learn the basics of literacy with intensive community-based instruction from skilled educators known as ALS Mobile Teachers. Arpillada (2018) stated that their duties and responsibilities range from facilitating learning sessions with students to fostering literacy and other relevant skills based on ALS competencies. Along with carrying out action-research activities, they also create and maintain a functional networking and reporting system. They also carry out other related tasks and obligations. The mobile teachers were also young adults, primarily men. Although they were capable academically, their official training had been designed to manage formal courses. To advance their careers, several mobile instructors have completed postgraduate coursework in administration and supervision. Despite being relatively new to teaching as mobile teachers, they had all passed the Licensure Examination for Instructors (Department of Education, 2019).

In addition, Schoone et al. (2022) ALS teacher (9–12) prepares and leads activities, supervises students, monitors their progress, and evaluates their performance. The ALS Teacher oversees the curriculum for the Community Access Training, Math, Science, and English/Reading subjects. The homeroom teacher also has the option to teach. The use of rehabilitative equipment, transportation, personal care, and range of motion may all require physical assistance. Attending IEP meetings and working on IEP tasks with other members of the student assessment team are requirements for the ALS Teacher. The transition is a significant

worry for a student as graduation draws near. Communications with all parties involved in the student's education must be handled by the ALS Teacher. Also, a record of students is kept by the ALS Instructor.

Like the ALS Teacher, also known as the Mobile Teacher (MT), the Civil Service Commission has designated the ALS Teacher as a Department of Education (DepEd) teacher. This person is employed by the Department of Budget and Management (DBM) (Resurrection et al., 2021). As noted by Pablo (2021), the term "Teacher" will refer to all Mobile Teachers collectively. Additionally, part-time, or full-time DepEd teachers appointed to the ALS program in their districts serve as ALS Coordinators (DSC) (Department of Education, 2019). As a result, all District ALS Coordinators stationed throughout the neighborhood will go by the name "Teacher". It is also assumed that when the Mobile Teacher/DALSC meets all the requirements, he or she becomes eligible for promotion to the next level. They may then be promoted to the positions of Master Teacher, School Head, or Supervisor at the district, division, or regional levels, in compliance with the CSC qualification criteria (Llego, 2019).

C. Challenges in Managing the Implementation of Alternative Learning System

Teachers' roles are challenging. To put it plainly, they may be assigned to difficult-to-reach places where flying to and from is not always simple (Teresa, 2020 as cited in Chavez & Tadena, 2021). Furthermore, less than 1% of the overall national education budget was spent on ALS and mobile teachers over the course of the previous 10 years. Mobile teachers in CLCs must come up with creative strategies to ensure appropriate seating, tables, and learning tools most of the time because there are not enough resources to build learning centers and buy educational materials, according to mobile instructors. They also used their own money to duplicate modules, purchase paper and ink, and even pay for meals for some of their students' projects (Penuels, 2020).

Notably, according to Yu (2018), one of the most significant challenges in implementing an ALS program is the lack of a favorable and well-structured classroom environment; all ALS learners need a well-organized learning environment. It seems that not everyone can benefit from the opportunity. As elaborated by Labarrete (2021), ALS learners will be more engaged in obtaining information or learning new abilities than other students. When it comes to presenting their ideas confidently in front of their peers, classroom instruction instills conflict resolution skills and working with people from different cultural backgrounds. Classroom instruction also teaches students to get along with people from different cultural backgrounds.

Similarly, the Department of Education (2019) provided advantages and disadvantages for ALS teachers and underprivileged students, and they gained new perspectives on this type of learning methodology. ALS students face several challenges that prevent them from completing their formal education. The most frequently expressed concerns, which the learners readily acknowledged, were family issues and financial difficulties (Saidu & Ibrahim, 2021). Due to the learners' jobs and other distractions, the mobile teacher stated that she finds it difficult to maintain complete attendance. Some students may leave for a month or two without notice and then return after a few house visits and encouragement to finish their education (Ruiz et al., 2020).

The issue with our disparate levels of education, according to Odey and Opoh (2019), is not how policies are created, but rather how the Senior High School Curriculum is implemented. Even though much money is spent on implementing new curricula, some of these attempts have been unsuccessful. The main reason it did not work is that experts from both inside and outside the school system did not comprehend the school's culture. Due to inadequate training and orientation, teachers struggle to adjust to their new positions. Knowing how people in the school system share power, their traditions, and their roles and responsibilities will help you implement the curriculum successfully.

In addition, Arpilleda (2018) stated that four issues have emerged in ALS: a lack of teaching materials; a delay in the allocation of allowances; the lack of a permanent budget waiver; the lack of a learning center and other services; and inconsistent ALS undergraduate attendance. He claimed that many mobile teachers were dissatisfied with the lack of assistance from local legislators and the large number of students attending their sessions. Gibbons (2020) also mentioned the school's lack of support as a barrier to launching an alternative learning system program. ALS is unacceptable in the classroom, according to both teachers and students. Students believe their work is valuable because of the open nature of the school environment. Intentionally combining diversity and inclusion improves student performance, retention, creativity, and innovation as well as lowers absenteeism and dropout rates, according to the National Center for Education Statistics (2022). Diversity and inclusion are based then on the understanding that everyone has inherent worth and that opposing viewpoints are possible (Kearney et al., 2022).

Moreover, according to Maslow (2020), many mobile teachers have difficulties obtaining the required educational resources given the state financing that has been granted to them. Frequently, teachers must utilize their cash to maintain a fully working classroom and satisfy the requirements of all their pupils. Supplies, equipment, and resources significantly influence how effective and easy learning is possible. There is something for everyone, from simple books, pamphlets, boards, and chalk to more advanced tools such as computers and laboratory equipment. Everything consists of educational materials and assistance.

In support, Teresa (2020) held that mobile teachers believe that making the most of teaching aids would have a favorable influence on academic quality. Mobile teachers' effective use of teaching aids enhances the learning process and plays a critical role in making students learn real and palpable. It also aids in the retention of what pupils have studied throughout the study. Similarly, there was a significant variation in the readiness of public schools, as well as the readiness of their respective mobile teachers, when it came to implementing the ALS Senior High School programs in terms of teaching skills, teaching strategies, and teaching materials, and this was primarily due to the different settings and conditions in which the new program was being implemented. Although they were willing to participate in the program, they still do not find themselves equipped to teach students because they believe they need more training (Tamayo, 2021).

In addition, the study by Maffe (2020) quantified that the most urgent issue at hand is the severe lack of resources present in schools. This problem affects the teachers and the students, and it may also have an impact on the parents of the students. When there are not enough resources available in the classrooms, it can make both students and teachers feel extremely uneasy. Both students and teachers are suffering from emotional distress because of the inadequate resources being made available to them, and they are also unable to learn as effectively as they could. When we have a better understanding of the issues at hand, we will be able to begin looking into potential solutions to this difficult challenge.

Furthermore, the Philippine education system's objective has always been to develop exceptional undergraduates at the primary, elementary, and junior high school levels. The Department of Education has announced the establishment of ALS Senior High School, which all Filipinos believe would benefit them. While everyone involved in this transformation will have a unique experience, this is particularly true for those closest to them: family members, instructors, and learners. However, special obstacles occur during the execution of the ALS Senior High School program, including a lack of understanding of implementation standards, a lack of implementation resources, and a lack of training for Mobile Teachers (Lalu, 2021).

Concerns about the teachers' lack of curricular fidelity surfaced during the process of developing the senior high school curriculum. The connection that makes identifying the concerns of teachers pertinent to the currently proposed study is the need to comprehend potential barriers that may hinder instructors when they are required to implement a new curriculum for senior high school. It will be possible to increase the success rate by addressing these issues both before and during the curriculum implementation process and by giving administrators the necessary resources to support teachers as they navigate curriculum changes (Arpilleda, 2018).

Moreover, curriculum implementation refers to the regular activities that take place in the classroom and in which the teacher participates in the student's level of achievement and tracks their progress in the curriculum. The newly implemented curriculum in senior high school is the responsibility of the teachers, and it is they must whether it is having the desired impact on the student's academic performance or not. To complete the tasks assigned to them, teachers rely on the curriculum's materials, the teaching strategy, their own prior experiences, and their understanding of the curriculum's content. Teachers must be knowledgeable about the senior high school curriculum and have received the necessary training (Lynch & Mannion, 2021).

On the other hand, the curriculum guide is yet another issue raised. A specific educational program's pedagogy, goals, objectives, learning experiences, instructional resources, and evaluations are all described in this well-organized document. An example of this kind of document is a curriculum map which provides an explanation of what students should know and be able to do, which aids teachers in understanding how students should understand and be able to perform tasks. Teaching it to senior high school students is very challenging because it is impossible to educate students without a curriculum. But without a curriculum, education is impossible (Karakuş, 2019).

D. Support Needed for Alternative Learning System- Senior High School

Schools in the Philippines, particularly for teachers and supervisors, are in desperate need of training and seminars (Villanueva, 2021). SEAMEO INNOTECH organized a training session to help ALS teachers, specifically ALS Senior High School teachers, develop their abilities to provide high-quality programs to students. The training course will benefit mobile teachers and district supervisors because it will help them better understand the changing environment in which they operate and improve their abilities in managing themselves and developing constructive relationships with their stakeholders. The training session aims to increase ALS implementer cooperation in learning exchanges, ALS advocacy, and ALS implementer collaboration.

Interestingly, according to Maslow (2020), to successfully execute the Alternative Learning System Senior High School Program, the government must consider financial considerations. The government, however, has scarce financial resources, as revealed by Zaini et al. (2021). It is extremely difficult for many public schools to receive enough funding from the state to support their educational needs. For the benefit of all their students and to maintain a fully functional classroom, teachers frequently use their own money. The materials, tools, and resources available make learning more practical and effective. From books, leaflets, boards, and chalk, to more complex tools like computers and laboratory equipment. Educator resources and tools are included in everything. Also, educational experts and thinkers emphasize the crucial and decisive role that educational technology plays in the teaching-learning process at ALS – SHS, as stated by the Department of Education (2020). Besides, they

think that utilizing teaching resources effectively will improve the standard of instruction. The right kind of instruction provided by teachers is helpful to learning and essential to producing concrete learning. Students benefit from increased learning retention as well.

Additionally, Borela (2020) suggested that the Department of Education must develop the appropriate techniques to give immediate solutions to all the challenges discovered to guarantee that the objectives of this new curriculum can be met and realized. Numerous challenges must be addressed, and support requirements must be prioritized in the implementation of ALS-SHS. For instance, the participation of mobile teachers in various training and seminars must be maximized to ensure that they possess the necessary competencies and skills to deal with the students who have been included in this new program.

Similarly, ALS Senior High School teachers' training in 21st-century abilities such as critical thinking, problem-solving, and communication must be a top emphasis if they are part of a globally competitive and productive workforce. For students to achieve success in the classroom, administrators and instructors must collaborate. This implies that to execute the ALS Senior High School curriculum, knowledge, and experience are required to enhance competence and a positive attitude, which will help schools address issues and implement change. In addition, principals should recognize the needs of their personnel and incorporate those requirements into the overall needs of the school community (Calub, 2019). To better serve their students and advance their professional careers in education, teachers must constantly learn new skills, according to Barnido (2021). Additionally, to effectively instruct seniors in high school, teachers must constantly advance their knowledge. Also, senior high school instructors are required to use their subject-matter expertise when instructing students in a particular track.

The abovementioned review of related literature reveals that the implementation of ALS Senior High School plays an important purpose in the education sector to eradicate the population of out-of-school youth and adults. The presented literature also shows that mobile teachers play an important role in the implementation of ALS – SHS. The mobile teachers are committed to their duties and responsibilities to give quality education to out-of-school youth and adults. However, the presented literature emphasizes that mobile teachers in ALS encountered different difficulties and limitations in managing the implementation of ALS senior high. As a result, mobile teachers cannot fully sustain the effective implementation of ALS in senior high schools. Hence, the reviewed literature firmly explicates that the ALS mobile teachers needed some support and assistance to completely implement the ALS senior high school program.

CHAPTER THREE METHODOLOGY

This chapter discusses the research methodology used to collect and analyze the data used in this study. Additionally, this chapter discusses the research design and participants, the researcher's role, data sources and analysis, data collection techniques, the study's trustworthiness, and ethical considerations.

A. Research Design

This study was conducted using a qualitative research technique, specifically the phenomenological approach, to explore the lived experiences of mobile teachers who manage ALS senior high school implementation. For Denzin and Lincoln (2019), qualitative research implements and collects a variety of experimental materials, including surveys; personal experiences and introspection; life stories; interviews; artifacts; exploratory; cultural or historical; immersive; and visual texts that describe both routine and difficult moments and significance in persons' lives.

In this study, the qualitative design was employed to explore the lived experiences of ALS mobile teachers who manage the implementation of ALS senior high school. This research method helped me identify and collect the personal challenges and coping strategies of ALS mobile teachers in providing administration to ALS senior high schools in the Division of Tagum City. Furthermore, it explored the practices of ALS mobile teachers who are assigned to handle the ALS senior high school.

On the other hand, phenomenology is interested in studying the experience of objects and the acts of consciousness by and through which these objects are disclosed (Creswell, 2018). In addition, the phenomenological approach also aims to shed light on a particular issue by identifying phenomena in terms of how people experience them in a certain circumstance. In research, this is usually translated to using inductive or qualitative approaches to obtain deep knowledge and perspectives (Williams, 2021).

In this study, phenomenology was used since the major purpose is to elucidate the meaning of the participants' lived experiences as mobile instructors. Additionally, doing phenomenology research was important since it elicited the most precise data on mobile teachers' lived experiences in managing the ALS senior high school program's implementation. Additionally, it helped me to avoid my preexisting notions about the topic of the research from distorting the viewpoints of the participants.

Consequently, the qualitative phenomenology approach is suited for investigating the lived experiences of mobile teachers who manage the implementation of ALS senior high school since it exposed their personal experiences in managing the implementation of ALS senior high school. By using this research strategy, I thoroughly obtained the experiences of the participants who are specialists in their personal experiences as they supervise the implementation of ALS in senior high school. As Creswell (2018) made clear, focus group discussions (FGD) and in-depth interviews (IDI) were employed since qualitative research, as opposed to quantitative research, characterizes the environment as personal rather than scientific. A frequent technique for gathering data, focusing attention, and understanding an individual's human experiences is to have them tell their lived experiences related to their management's implementation of the ALS senior high school program.

Moreover, this study utilized focus group discussions (FGD) and in-depth interviews (IDI) that served as primary methods to obtain the data. In the selection of participants, this study utilized purposive sampling. In addition, during data analysis, this study used thematic analysis wherein the replies from discussions and interviews were extensively examined. Moreover, this research followed the trustworthiness of the study to generate confidence and constancy in the data. Lastly, this study was fair and did not harm the participants by adhering to ethical considerations.

B. Research Participants

In this phenomenological study, 10 selected participants took part in interviews as representatives of ALS mobile teachers from DepEd Tagum City Division. There were three (3) participants in in-depth (IDI). In contrast, seven (7) joined in a Focus Group Discussion (FGD). The selection of 10 participants was based on the idea of Creswell (2018) that a minimum of three (3) participants and a maximum of 15 participants is valid in doing phenomenological qualitative research. Thus, the 10 selected ALS mobile teachers served as participants in this study.

Moreover, this qualitative-phenomenological study utilized purposive sampling in selecting the participants for this study. The purposive sampling method ensured that all the participants were willing to explain their administrative involvement and insights as mobile teachers. Kumar et al. (2020) elucidated that purposive sampling is used before conducting the study to achieve adequate breadth and depth of information. Also, purposive sampling is a technique widely used in qualitative research to get a full knowledge of all participants who match specified pre-determined criteria (Creswell, 2018).

Furthermore, the participants of this study were chosen based on the following criteria: (a) designated as an ALS mobile teacher in the Division of Tagum City; (b) a mobile teacher assigned to manage the implementation of the ALS senior high school program (3) a mobile teacher for at least 3 years in the service. Meanwhile, mobile teachers who are not assigned to manage the implementation of ALS – Senior High School in the Division of Tagum are excluded from this research. Also, all the identified

participants were given the right to withdraw their participation in this study even before the issuance of the Informed Consent Form (ICF). Finally, these mobile teachers were selected to provide maximum or diverse modification of participants to obtain more insights into the inquiry of this study.

C. Role of the Researcher

The researcher is responsible for analyzing the information and identifying patterns that may disclose previously unknown features of the experiences of human beings and must do a range of activities during the duration of the study (Creswell, 2018).

I gathered and analyzed data for this study, which significantly contributed to the success of the investigation. Furthermore, I made sure that the qualitative study used appropriate data collection techniques.

As someone who ensures the ethical conduct of research, I affirmed and went after ethical principles all over the period of this research. In addition, I took precautions to avoid causing harm over the course of this qualitative investigation. I ensured that all participants' individualities were safeguarded to the greatest degree. Additionally, I protected all written data/responses, as well as the video/audio recordings, in a password-protected folder on a password-protected laptop. Moreover, I asked my research adviser to guarantee that the entire data were examined systemically.

As an interviewer for the In-Depth Interviews (IDIs) and moderator for the Focus Group Discussion (FGD), I ensured that participants got the validated guiding questions before the virtual interview sessions. Throughout the In-Depth Interviews, I ensured that the three (3) participants were comfortable in their places. Additionally, I ensured that they had independence and sufficient time to express their experiences. Meanwhile, as the Focus Group Discussion moderator, I guaranteed that all participants agreed on the FGD's timetable. I guaranteed that the FGD ran well and that each participant had the chance to disclose their experiences in the discussions. Notably, during the IDI and FGD, I applied probing questions to obtain clarification and a thorough understanding of their experiences.

As someone who ensures that the entire interview is recorded correctly, I recorded the complete interviews through Google Meet or Zoom Teleconference's record tool. Then, I made sure that approval was obtained from each participant to record the whole interview. Through this, I ensured to quickly transcribe and comprehend the information.

As transcriber and encoder of the responses of the participants, I made certain that all replies from participants were accurately transcribed. I meticulously transcribed the responses to confirm the authenticity and integrity of the data. Upon transcribing the replies, I guaranteed that all participants were allocated codes to conceal their identities. Additionally, by accurately transcribing the replies, I had a better comprehension of the answers. Through this, I was able to evaluate the data more efficiently.

As someone who translates the responses of participants to standard English format, I ensured the correctness of the translated data. I guaranteed that all replies in the local dialect during the implementation of virtual meetings/interviews were faithfully translated. Throughout the translation process, I strived to remove my prejudices to guarantee that the participants were treated fairly. This way, I ensured the data's consistency and authenticity.

As a primary data analyst of this study, I guaranteed that I implemented systematic techniques while analyzing the participants' replies. I undertook an in-depth analysis of transcribed data to completely extract the replies' relevant context. Then, I employed thematic analysis to generate fundamental themes by identifying the data's underlying contexts. Also, in analyzing the data, my research adviser guided me in assessing the data to ensure that every data was thoroughly analyzed.

D. Data Sources

Qualitative research employs a variety of data-collecting techniques (Creswell, 2017). Data sources are often acquired using a variety of approaches, including observation, documentation, and interviews. However, the primary data for this research was acquired via Focus Group Discussions and In-Depth Interviews. Additionally, the key sources of data were the responses of ALS mobile teachers in the Division of Tagum City based on their personal experiences in managing the implementation of the ALS Senior High School program.

In-Depth Interviews (IDI) are used to ascertain a group's shared experiences (Bhandari 2020). In this study, three (3) participants engaged in in-depth interviews as part of this research. This group of participants was homogenous, and they were questioned using similar guiding questions. All participants had the opportunity to tell their experiences. Subsequently, follow-up questions were used to collect further information and clarify participants' answers. Additionally, the goal of the In-Depth Interviews (IDI) was to extract detailed information on the problems faced by ALS mobile teachers in managing ALS Senior High School.

Meanwhile, Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) are used to ascertain a group of persons' views, perspectives, and perceptions about a certain phenomenon (Bhandari, 2020). In this study, the Focus Group Discussion (FGD) had seven (7) participants. In the conduct of Focus Group Discussions (FGD), participants were required to discuss and exchange ideas to generate different points of view on the phenomenon being studied. Additionally, participants in the FGD were allowed to voice their ideas and opinions and to urge their peers to do so as well, particularly if their experiences are comparable. Further, the purpose of Focus Group Discussions (FGD) in this study was to provide a valuable understanding of the experiences of ALS mobile teachers in managing the supervision of ALS Senior High School.

Additionally, this study relied on secondary sources such as journals, papers, and books to reflect the diverse experiences, perspectives, conclusions, and data gathered from many researchers and publications. These secondary sources were utilized in this research to provide context for the topic under investigation. These secondary sources were also used as supporting literature and reference materials throughout the study's presentation of the results.

E. Data Collection Procedure

In qualitative research, normally, data are acquired via interviews, dialogues, focus group discussions, and examination of articles (Creswell, 2018). In this study, I conducted virtual interviews to fully obtain data about the mobile teachers' experiences in managing the ALS senior high school program. To fulfill the study's ethical standard, I must follow step-by-step processes for gathering data. Hence, purposive sampling was used to identify individuals who were willing to discuss and convey their recruiting experiences.

As a researcher, I adhered to rigorous data-collecting procedures, including social distancing, wearing masks and face shields, and others, following IATF regulations for official face-to-face interactions. Additionally, I gathered data to attain the purpose of this research study. These entailed obtaining permission for the research, getting access, establishing rapport, and collecting, recording, and keeping data.

First, I sent my manuscript to SMCTI Research Ethics Committee to secure a certification to conduct research. Then, I prepared another endorsement letter signed by the Dean of the Graduate School of St. Mary's College, Inc. Afterwards, I sent the endorsement letter and other pertinent papers to the Tagum City Schools Division Superintendent Office, Tagum City, Davao del Norte, Philippines.

Second, after the Schools Division Superintendent of the Tagum City Division approved my request to conduct the study, I sent out a request letter to all selected mobile teachers in ALS to ask permission to participate in this study. With this, purposive sampling was used to select these participants. It is an approach for acquiring extensive data from participants. I chose participants' ability and willingness to discuss their experiences, reality, and the research-specific criteria.

Third, as soon as the selected participants accepted the call for participation, I conducted a one-on-one virtual orientation for all the participants. During the conduct of the virtual orientation, I ensured to discuss the framework and the purpose of this qualitative study. Also, I guaranteed that the guidelines and criteria for the study methodologies are presented. I presented the necessary procedures for undertaking the In-Depth Interviews (IDIs) and Focus Group Discussions (FGD). I also discussed the rights and privileges of the participants, such as the confidentiality of their identities and the opportunity to withdraw from participation. Following that, I reminded them to sign an Informed Consent Form (ICF) indicating their voluntary participation and full understanding of this qualitative research.

Fourth, before doing a virtual interview, I got authorization from the selected participants to record the whole conversation. Thus, it enabled me to check participant replies and thoroughly scrutinize the data. Then, before the virtual interview, I sent interview guide questions in advance to assist the participants in preparing their replies. Also, by reading the advance questions they could determine the general interview structure in terms of question flow.

Thereafter, I employed Google Meet or Zoom Teleconference to perform Focus Group Discussions (FGD) and In-depth Interviews (IDI) throughout the interview process. Then, 15 minutes before the planned time of the interview, I provided the meeting link to each participant through Messenger. Thus, before I began interviewing participants, I notified them that the interview would last between 40 and 60 minutes and that all replies would be treated with the greatest anonymity by giving them code names. Before I began asking questions in the In-Depth Interviews, I made sure that participants were at ease in their places. Additionally, the three (3) participants who undertook the In-Depth Interviews were given sufficient time and independence to discuss their perspectives. Meanwhile, before commencing the Focus Group Discussion, I ensured that all seven (7) participants had arrived. Then, throughout the discussions, I guaranteed that each participant felt secure for them to share their experiences with the other participants freely.

Fifth, following the conduct of data gathering, which is the virtual interviews, I immediately transcribed verbatim the responses to ensure greater correctness during the data analysis. Then, I ensured to translate the transcribed data into the Standard English Language. Afterward, I guaranteed that all my participants had the chance to check and review the transcribed data. To facilitate this, I transmitted the transcribed replies by online chat or e-mail. Thus, by enabling participants to verify the correctness of the transcribed data, bias and misquotation of the material may be avoided.

Sixth, after transcribing the data, I conducted initial data analysis immediately, wherein I began arranging the transcribed replies to my study questions. Then, I used thematic analysis to deconstruct the data's underpinning context to produce themes. Additionally, I was supervised by my data analyst and research adviser, to ensure the quality of the data analysis.

Finally, I shared the study's results with the research participants, so they verified the accuracy and truthfulness of the analyzed data. Importantly, I safeguarded the data I collected by storing it in a shared password-protected folder together with the audio recordings and papers, which ensure that participants' identities remain anonymous throughout the study. Additionally, I am the only keeper of the raw study materials, which were stored in a locked filing cabinet. After three years, this data will be destroyed accordingly.

F. Data Analysis

Ravindran (2019) explained that data analysis is an iterative and difficult process in qualitative research. Additionally, it is an important part of qualitative research. Whatever the data are, it is the analysis of the data that determines the study's findings in the most significant way. In this study, I guaranteed that all acquired and obtained data is displayed and evaluated extensively. Also, I made certain that the data analysis in this research shall anchor the needs and objectives of this research endeavor.

Creswell (2018) explained that qualitative data analysis involves on data collection, coding, and theme analysis. In this study, I prepared the transcribed data from the focus group discussion, in-depth interviews, written notes, and audio recordings.

Coding identifies concepts and findings relations between the responses. It is the procedure of analyzing qualitative text data by dissecting them and reassembling them in a meaningful manner (Creswell, 2018). Additionally, the same author explained that coding also identifies concepts and findings connections between the data collected. It links ideas to other ideas from the data in this research.

In this study, I employed codes to assist me in making a data-driven conclusion based on the replies of the participants. Then, throughout the coding process, I assigned appropriate code names to each piece of data, which aided me in correctly analyzing and summarizing the replies of the participants during the IDI and FGD. Thus, I used codes for words and phrases in each response that could help to capture what the answer is about.

Thematic analysis, on the other hand, is regarded as the most fundamental tool of qualitative research. As stated by Cartwright (2020), the goal of thematic analysis is to find patterns of meaning across data that are relevant to the research issue. Additionally, the same author highlighted that thematic analysis happens after relevant data has been coded and allocated to a subject or category.

In this study, I investigated the codes and finally uncover the fundamental concept that produced key themes. Then, using the coded data, I determined the themes. Additionally, I conducted in-depth research and explanation of each theme, supplemented by suitable literature to ensure the authenticity of the themes generated during thematic analysis. Commonly, the central purpose of getting themes from the participants' responses is to produce answers to the study's research questions. Lastly, I also sought the help of my data analyst to check the correctness of my initial analysis.

G. Trustworthiness of the Study

In qualitative research, the trustworthiness of the study is significant for establishing the consistency and validity of the findings. Also, the trustworthiness of the study serves as support to the claim that the findings of the study are worth noting. Rallis (2007) cited that Lincoln and Guba constructed criteria to address the trustworthiness of a study that includes credibility, confirmability, transferability, and dependability.

Credibility can be defined as credible information, which can be depended on after being precise and correct (Lazar et al., 2018). Also, credibility refers to the underlying notion of the conclusions derived from the data gathered and demonstrates the study's internal validity. Credibility comprises clearly explained research methodologies, iterative questioning, and member checking to ensure that the research approach and data acquired from participants' viewpoints and experiences are constant and correct (Korstjens & Moser, 2018).

In this study, to guarantee credibility, I made sure that this research underwent a rigorous process. By executing this procedure, I was able to present a well-explained research method. Additionally, I was able to provide an in-depth description of how the participants were chosen. Similarly, I presented a well-established description of the research locale of this study. I also ensured that a detailed discussion of the research design for this study is included.

Iterative questioning is a data collection approach that entails returning to previously delivered questions and recreating them to elicit more information. Additionally, iterative questioning is a structured turn of phrase for the process by which the researcher revisits previously mentioned topics and focuses on important information via revised questions (Korstjens & Moser, 2018).

In this study, I employed iterative questioning to elicit thorough responses from the participants to execute the major research method of this study. I ensured to employ this as a substantial data-gathering approach, in which I revisited the topics that the participants had previously mentioned and focused on relevant information via reworded questioning. In this way, I identified and dismissed notions that conflict with one another. In addition, I used probing questions during participant interviews, especially if their replies need to be more inclusive, to diversify the data and make it simpler to code.

On the other hand, member checking is a technique that establishes the reliability of findings by redistributing the analyzed findings to participants for data verification. It was emphasized that the language used by participants should be consistent with the message they were trying to express. To ensure that participants get findings that have been verified and evaluated, member checking was employed in this research. To complete the final member verification procedure, participants receive a copy of the transcribed data (Birth et al., 2018).

In this study, to facilitate member checking, I allowed each participant to verify the results independently. In this manner, I was able to ensure that each participant agreed and confirmed the correctness and validity of the transcription of the data. Following that, I asked participants to sign a certificate confirming that they had evaluated and acknowledged the correctness of the findings of the study. Moreover, this substantiates the participants' assertion that the analyzed data are their own experiences.

Dependability is an evaluation of the study results' quality. When doing qualitative research, dependability is significant since it discloses that the conclusions are more consistent and repeatable than the original data as explained by (Birth et al. 2018; Shenton, 2004). This includes overlapping strategies and a clear description of methodologies. The overlapping approach takes use of methodological triangulation, or the integration of different data collection techniques such as interviews and surveys, to get overlapping and cross-validating data (Birth et al. 2018).

In this study, I conducted Focus Group Discussions (FGD) and In-depth Interviews (IDIs) using a validated interview guide questionnaire. I made certain that all the questions were suitable to meet the study's goal of answering the research questions. I ensured that all the sub-questions in the interview guide questionnaire were useful in eliciting accurate information about the participants' experiences as ALS mobile teachers in the Division of Tagum City. Through this, I was able to thoroughly examine and assess the responses provided by the participants.

Moreover, I was accountable for ensuring that the methodologies used in the research were legitimate, traceable, and thoroughly documented. In this manner, future researchers will be able to duplicate this study, even if the identical result is unnecessary, by presenting an organized and clear description of the research method and design. Also, the readers may then examine whether this study adhered to approved research standards and procedures. Importantly, the dependability of this qualitative inquiry is significant since it demonstrates that the conclusions are more constant and reproducible than the raw data.

Similarly, I discussed the data collection procedures, which include Focus Group Discussion and In-depth Interviews, to demonstrate the dependability of the study's findings. Additionally, I depended solely on information acquired from In-depth Interviews and Focus Group discussions as the main sources of data. Also, I focused on making sure that all the information gathered during the inquiry is derived from replies provided by participants in virtual interviews.

Furthermore, to ensure the study's reliability and consistency, I made sure that all the information gathered during Focus Group discussions and in-depth interviews was accurately documented. Also, in transcribing and translating the replies, I used extreme caution to preserve and retain all the participants' shared thoughts and ideas. Further, throughout the data analysis process, I ensured that my research adviser and data analyst confirm the validity of the information acquired during the virtual interviews.

Confirmability establishes that the researcher's interpretations and findings are obtained from the data, and such requires the researcher to explain how such conclusions and analyses are reached (Saldaña, 2019). Confirmability is a term that refers to the exact methodological requirements that enable the study's findings to be examined for validity (Shenton, 2004). Additionally, the triangulation and audit trail are included to enable the evaluation of the validity of the study results.

The audit trail is a strategy for verifying wherever information is omitted, or unsuitable actions occur. Also, it determines if the process is utilized efficiently and fairly while conforming to all applicable standards (Dacalus, 2019). Additionally, the same author indicates that an audit trail will strengthen the credibility and transparency of the research.

In this study, I produced an audit trail to document participant replies during Focus Group discussions and In-depth Interviews. This audit trail served as physical evidence to support and corroborate the results and conclusions that I obtained as an outcome of my data analysis. In creating an audit trail, I was upfront in the way I used the raw data, ensuring that all the participants' responses were presented properly and completely. I made certain that this audit trail is comprehensive and easily available to readers. Through this technique, the readers may be able to follow the outcomes while also understanding how the data were evaluated. At the same time, readers could see the raw data.

Furthermore, the audit trail aided me in comprehending my study since I assigned codes to each participant, allowing me to trace their responses effortlessly and quickly. To provide complete confirmability, I made use of an audit trail with coding categorization. IDI (n) and FGD (n) codes were used to denote the order in which participants were questioned and the kind of interview in which they participated. This coding approach enabled me in maintaining the confidentiality of the participants' information. Additionally, I produced a comprehensive audit trail since it served as evidence if the research panel members and my thesis adviser want specific documentation regarding the data sources throughout the investigation.

Meanwhile, triangulation is a procedure that is often used in research to aid the researcher in confirming the data by cross-checking it against two or more responses or data from other sources during the interview (Dacalus, 2019). Additionally, this method is required to eliminate researcher bias throughout the data collection and analysis processes.

In this study, triangulation is critical since I profoundly established confirmability. Also, I utilized triangulation to reduce bias by cross-checking the two or more replies of participants to verify the themes. As a researcher, I had 10 participants for the two (2) techniques of gathering the data used in the context of this research. For an in-depth interview, I had a total of three (3) participants and seven (7) participants for Focus Group Discussion. This improved data quality from various sources while also reducing bias. The replies of the mobile teachers, in addition to being a good source of information for triangulation, may also be used to demonstrate the validity of the data.

Finally, **transferability** refers to the extent to which the results can be applied to a wide range of contexts with a variety of respondents – it is the qualitative equivalent of generalizability (Spake, 2022). In other words, if researchers or readers think their conditions are like those discussed in the research study, they may apply the results to their situations. In addition, a thorough explanation of the research method was employed, as well as the criteria used to select participants. A detailed explanation of the method used was included to ensure external validity. Also included is a detailed explanation of the research site and data collection methods. To ensure that this study is transferable in a variety of contexts, detailed information about the participant selection criteria, the research site, and the study methodology is provided. Readers who believe that any of the issues raised in this study are similar to their own may be able to relate to the findings as a result.

In addition, I provided a thorough discussion of the approach used in this qualitative investigation. I discussed in great depth the data-gathering processes used in this study. I presented a thorough explanation of why phenomenology and qualitative methodologies are suited for this investigation. Additionally, for future reference and to reduce the risk of bias in the data collection and analysis, I kept all the data analyses in case other researchers may become interested in checking them. With this, I was able to verify the results autonomously, and readers will be able to verify that any conclusions were taken from the raw data.

H. Ethical Considerations

The goal of ethical considerations in this study is to serve as a guide in ensuring the safety and well-being of the participants. The researcher is responsible for ensuring the human rights of all study participants. Adhering to the National Ethical Guidelines (2017), primarily on online data collection, helps to facilitate this. This ensures the confidentiality of all research participants. Significantly, it includes respect for persons, beneficence, and justice, as cited by Akaranga et al. (2018).

Respect for Persons highlights the importance of treating research participants as autonomous individuals. Participants are autonomous, independent, and capable of making decisions on their own if provided with adequate knowledge to do so. This idea underpins informed consent (Creswell, 2017).

In this research, I ensured that mobile educators get an Informed Consent Form (ICF) before participation in the study. I utilized the Informed Consent Form to explain the study's purpose, how participants are selected anchored on the inclusion criteria, and the advantages and risks related to participation in this qualitative study. In addition, after the selected participants accepted my offer, each one of them waded to complete the Informed Consent Form as proof that they voluntarily engaged in this study on their own decision. Importantly, participants were granted the right to withdraw from the research at any point throughout its duration. In addition, I safeguarded the security of the personal data of the participants by assigning them code names and ensuring that any information acquired from them is kept with utmost confidentiality.

Moreover, I also guaranteed that the mobile teachers in all IDI and FGD interviews have given me their written consent before recording them so that this practice does not go in contradiction with their interests. The whole interview was executed virtually at a time that was convenient for all participants to adhere to the COVID-19 safety and health requirements set by the IATF (Inter-Agency Task Force). Through this, I was able to preserve the welfare and well-being of the participants.

Beneficence entails a commitment to minimizing the risks of harm and maximizing the participants' benefits (Adams, 2018). It is a moral responsibility to do things for the benefit of others, using and preserving their well-being and avoiding or eradicating any potential damage that may arise because of the conduct.

In this study, I ensured that all participants remained anonymous by assigning them code names within the context of the study. This is to safeguard their privacy since their views and perspectives may conflict with those of others, leading to miscommunications. Additionally, I guaranteed that no identifiable information about the participants or their assigned schools was disclosed. I also ensured that interviews were conducted at a time that was convenient for the participants since I was held accountable for their security and comfort. As part of this endeavor, I followed the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF)-mandated health protocols for COVID-19 response, which assisted in minimizing risks associated with the study's conduct, including dangers to participants' health and safety.

In this study, I ensured that the findings of this research had a direct benefit to all the participants. As a researcher, it is my responsibility to maximize the direct benefits for all the participants. I guaranteed that participants made this research their platform to create awareness in society about their struggles as mobile teachers that provide management in the implementation of ALS-SHS. With this, all participants directly benefited from this study, as they had the chance to be heard and recognized by various individuals or organizations such as the Department of Education.

Justice refers to all persons (regardless of race, gender, ethnic origin, or age) who must be equitably exposed to the study's risks and benefits. Individuals should be involved or excluded only to address study inquiries or hypotheses (Buchanan, 1987).

The principle of justice required the researcher to be fair to the participants. Thus, this research was conducted equitably. All participants in my study were treated equally and fairly. Also, I gave particular attention to those who obtained a minor benefit from the virtual interview, such as those with poor internet connections. As a researcher, I wanted to reassure my participants about this problem by offering and compensating them for the financial resources required to maintain a steady internet connection. The interview was conducted through virtual meetings; hence participants were allowed to select their place and time. Importantly, I gave a token of gratitude to all the research participants as a symbol of my appreciation for their effort and time.

Consequently, all mobile teachers who are assigned to manage the implementation of the ALS senior high school program received full credit for their time, effort, and most of all, their interest in sharing their experiences. Additionally, participants were assured that as the researcher of this study, I am competent enough as I had completed all academic criteria for admittance to the SMCTI - Graduate School Program. Further, I trusted my thesis adviser, who is suitably equipped to oversee this study considering his high educational background, distinction, and competence.

In addition to Belmont's Report, I also had a strict adherence to the **Data Privacy Act of 2012** (Republic Act No. 10173), which protects individuals in the unpermitted administration of individual data that is (1) private, not openly available; and (2) recognizable, such that the individual's distinctiveness is obvious either directly or when combined with other publicly available information.

In the context of the study, to guard the participants' privacy, I allocated them appropriate code names. From written to audio files, all data collected were placed in a password-protected folder on a laptop and in locked/protected cabinets accessible only to me. The data gathered will be stored for three (3) years after the research project concluded, and after such time it will be securely destroyed to prevent unlicensed use or revelation to any other party or the public, or as mandatory by applicable law.

Moreover, I verified that all standards were followed to safeguard the participants' well-being, prevent possible manipulation of the data, and thereby promote the quest for knowledge and truth, which are the major aims of the study. Additionally, I upheld ethical standards to ensure that the public supports and believes in the study. Thus, how these ethical problems were addressed has a significant influence on the integrity of this research.

Importantly, from participating in this study, all the participants who were allowed to engage in this personal experience, participants in this research directly benefited from related personal growth in the future. This research has an indirect benefit for participants because it does not fully help them resolve all the arising problems in the ALS senior high school program. Thus, it allows them to share their experiences with the community.

CHAPTER FOUR RESULTS

This chapter presents the results of the study, which were extracted from the answers of participants to the research questions posed during the In-depth Interviews and Focus Group Discussion. The collected answers from participants underwent comprehensive analysis to obtain the core ideas and essential themes.

A. *The Lived Experiences of Mobile Teachers Managing the Implementation of ALS Senior High School*

Upon scrutinizing the answers of the participants regarding their lived experiences in managing the implementation of ALS Senior High School, four (4) themes were extracted: 1) difficulties and adjustments in teaching ALS – SHS; 2) unavailability of curriculum guide and LIS intended for ALS – SHS; 3) difficulties in producing modules and teaching materials; and 4) insufficiency of teachers for ALS – SHS.

Table 1 exhibits the major themes and core ideas on the lived experiences of Mobile Teachers Managing the Implementation of ALS Senior High School.

Table 1 Major Themes and Core Ideas on the Lived Experiences of Mobile Teachers Managing the Implementation of ALS Senior High School

Major Themes	Core Ideas
Difficulties and Adjustments in Teaching ALS – SHS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Having difficulty in teaching because of the lack of proper skills training and orientation • Having difficulty in teaching skills training to ALS – SHS TVL learners and hands-on interaction • Being challenged in teaching adult learners because of having a different field of specialization • Being challenged on making big adjustments to the implementation of the program • Having a hard time adjusting since the implementation of ALS – SHS and its system is not yet fully prepared.
Unavailability of Curriculum Guide	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using temporarily the curriculum of formal education • Having difficulty adapting the curriculum of formal education • Being challenged in handling ALS for Senior High School because of basing its curriculum on the formal education • Having modules that are not specifically designed with the curriculum for ALS – SHS since it is not yet available
Difficulties in Producing Modules and Teaching Materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encountering difficulties in producing modules for ALS – SHS due to the lack of budget • Having difficulty in providing more modules for ALS – SHS learners due to insufficient printing materials • Struggling in the procurement of teaching materials for ALS - SHS
Insufficiency of Teachers for ALS – SHS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Having a disproportionate number of available teachers • Shortage of teachers who specializes in skills training for ALS – SHS • Being challenged with the lack of well-trained teachers who should conduct instructions for ALS – SHS

➤ *Difficulties and Adjustments in Teaching ALS – SHS*

One of the collective lived experiences of the participants is having difficulties and adjustments in teaching ALS – SHS. As shared by the participants, they had difficulty in teaching ALS – SHS because of the lack of proper skills training and orientation. As such, they were also having a hard time adjusting since the implementation of ALS – SHS and its system is not yet fully prepared. Likewise, they were being challenged in making big adjustments on to implementation of the program and its system including the grading system. On the other hand, they were also being challenged in teaching ALS – SHS adult learners because they have different fields of specialization. Then, they were also having difficulty in teaching skills training to ALS – SHS TVL learners due to having no face-to-face hands-on.

- *This experience is associated with the shared answer of FGD-01 that stated:*

“If I will describe my experience as one of the teachers in the ALS Senior High School is that it is difficult. Because knowing that we don't have this proper training and proper orientation how to do these senior high school because, we know, I, you are also knowns mobile teacher na we don't have this training and we don't have this background. What bouton, how to teach senior high school because we as elementary education most of have us also secondary education major and has specific major but in senior high school, technically we are teaching naman din, I am teaching ALS Senior High School in TVL.”

(If I will describe my experiences as one of the teachers in the ALS Senior High School it is difficult, since knowing that we do not have proper training or orientation how to do this senior high school program. As a mobile teacher, we do not have the background on what or how to teach learners in ALS-SHS because we are degree holder of elementary or secondary education that has a specific major. However, in Senior high school technically I am teaching TVL. So, we have cookery, housekeeping and dressmaking, and FBS. With that, for us, it was hard since we did not undergo proper training.)

- *FGD-05 also shared that:*
“It is... it is hard for us to start because we do not have the training.”
- *IDI-01 supported this by sharing that:*
“There is no training yet for the mobile teacher or the ALS teacher.”
- *On the other hand, FGD-05 shared another difficulty:*
“There is no face-to-face. We cannot have the hands-on. So, it is hard for teacher teachers teach the cookery, the housekeeping, and the food beverage and servicing how to have the bed up, how and to cook. We just let the learners do their assignments at home because we do not have face-to-face. Even the senior high school students present at the school we are, we are teaching they are equipped with the equipment and materials but because of the pandemic, so it is hard to conduct the hands-on for the TVL in senior high school.”
- *IDI-03 also shared other problems on in Teaching ALS – SHS:*
“I can describe our implementation in managing the implementation of ALS senior high school we can say challenging. It's because at first some of the teachers in alternative learning systems alternative learning system is elementary or they are graduate in their graduate in Bachelor of sciences and Bachelor of Science in Elementary Education. And they will handle ALS Senior High School, imagine that. A teacher in elementary education will handle a higher education such as elementary school in which the subject of this program is not really similar to the elementary because when we say elementary, they are generalists.”
- *Similarly, IDI-01 shared that:*
“Based on my baccalaureate degree, I have a degree in elementary education. But in ALS, we are teaching adults and senior high school programs in which the subjects are on another level or need more knowledge. So, for me, it is really challenging because we are teaching this program; maybe I really have something to share.”
- *Then IDI-02 added that:*
“Aside sa akong na-mentioned nako is challenging, mao lang pud sya”
(Aside from what I have mentioned, it is also challenging.)
- *Furthermore, FGD-02 expressed that:*
“I think the thing that challenge us most as senior high school teacher is all about the system since...alam naman natin sa ALS we don't follow any grading system. Pasa ng portfolios si learner or either take ng exam sa learner. And because we follow these... from the formal system, of course we need to supply the need the grades that are needed sa mga bata... so it is a big adjustment not just for the learners but also for the teachers.”

(I think the thing that challenge us most as teacher in ALS-SHS is all about the system. As we all know, in ALS we do not follow any grading system. So, now students submit their portfolios or students take the exams, so we need to follow the grading system in formal education. Of course, we need to supply the grades that are needed by the learners. So, it is a big adjustment not just for the learners but also for us teachers.)

- *Likewise, IDI-01 shared same sentiment on having adjustments:*
“We are really having a hard time, because it's new to us. And also, I believe that during the first year, lisud jud siya... The lived experiences of mobile teachers are at the stage of the adjustment talaga... At that adjustment stage po during the coping up with the implementation of ALS senior high because this is our first year in implementing this. So, I know the system's not yet fully prepared or ready.”

(We are really having a hard time because it is new to us. And I believe that during the first year, it is really hard. The lived experiences of mobile teachers are still in the stage of adjustment. At that adjustment stage during the coping with the implementation of ALS senior high because this is our first year in implementing this. So, I know the system is not yet fully prepared or ready.)

➤ *Unavailability of Curriculum Guide and LIS Intended for ALS – SHS*

In this study, the participants shared that they experienced the unavailability of a curriculum guide and LIS intended for ALS – SHS. They have the same experience of using temporarily the curriculum of formal education due to the lack of concrete curriculum for ALS – SHS. Also, they had trouble in adapting to the curriculum of formal education because of having no curriculum intended for ALS in SHS. As a result, they were challenged in handling ALS for Senior High School because of basing its curriculum on the formal education. Then, they commonly encountered issues with having modules that are not specifically designed with the curriculum for ALS – SHS since it is not yet available. On the other hand, their main problem is having no separate Learner Information System (LIS) to enroll SHS – ALS learners.

- *This theme was supported by IDI-02 which clearly stated:*

“Also, we don't have a concrete curriculum that the ALS senior high will be...tawag ani, dapat na gamitun, kay we are using temporarily, the curriculum of formal school.”

(Also, we do not have a concrete curriculum that would align with the ALS-SHS program. For now, we are only using the SHS curriculum in formal education.)

- *FGD-01 expressed the same experience:*

“Our experience as a mobile teacher implementing the ALS senior high school, knowing that this is our first year in implementation, there are a lot of challenges and difficulties that we encounter. For particular, in the teaching and in teaching the curriculum of our senior high school because we know that we don't have this ALS curriculum, specifically focusing on the ALS Senior High School. So, we are just adapting the set, the formal setting or the formal curriculum, the curriculum of the formal education. So, I think the experience that we have is somewhat sort of difficult.”

- *FGD-03 supported the statement of FGD-01 by stating that:*

“So ngayon, this year lang sya na implement, yung senior high school. So... challenging dahil kailangan mong... kasi nagbi-base kasi kami sa ano, sa curriculum ng ALS, pero yung Senior High School, nagbi-base in a formal way. So challenging para sa mga teacher kung paano i-handle yung ALS senior high school.”

(So, this year we implemented the ALS-SHS. It is very challenging since we need to base our curriculum to Senior High School in formal setting. So, for us, the ALS-SHS is challenging to handle.)

- *FGD-03 then added that:*

“To us as teachers, it is really challenging because of the... we don't have curriculum that will support the program.”

- *Moreover, IDI-01 shared the same issue:*

“Sa ALS talaga na Senior High School and then also there's no module designed or aligned po sa curriculum ng ALS. Sharing lang po, same curriculum sa formal. And then ganun, wala din kaming own curriculum po.”

(There is no module designed or aligned to the curriculum of ALS-SHS. With that, we are only using the same curriculum in SHS in the formal education.)

- *IDI-03 also highlighted another problem:*

“Also, the LIS. We, the senior high school program doesn't have own LIS, in which to enroll our students.”

- *IDI-01 then supported by saying that:*

“Then we don't have our own LIS.”

➤ *Difficulties in Producing Modules and Teaching Materials*

The participants encountered difficulties in producing modules and teaching materials for the implementation of the ALS – SHS program specifically due to the lack of budget. Also, they had difficulty providing more modules for ALS – SHS learners. Moreover, they had difficulty in procuring teaching materials for ALS - SHS because of the lack of a direct contact person who should provide the needed materials.

- *In line with this, IDI-03 voiced that:*

“Actually, there are too many challenges that we have encountered in the implementation of ALS senior high school. And it's because this is the first time, of implementing the said program, there are two challenges. First, the budget... there are difficulties in producing modules, because lacking budget.”

- *FGD-05 also expressed that:*

“The ALS offers senior high school. And then, we have at first, we do not have the budget that is the number one problem.”

- *As such, IDI-01 clarified that:*
“Okay, first is there is no enough budget.”
- *In fact, IDI-03 expressed difficulties in producing modules and teaching materials:*
“Third, we need papers to provide more modules to the students. And that's it, that's the challenges that we have, it is very difficult for us to provide modules or modules for students.”
- *Furthermore, IDI-02 expressed an issue in producing teaching materials:*
“Also, ang mga materials nga gamitun, ang teacher pa ang mag-create, mag-provide, and also mag-agad pa ta manguha ug soft copy, nga mangutana pa ta sa formal school, nga ay asa, what are the modules for this quarter release? Wala tay, kana ganing direct person nga syay muhatag sa atoa, gamitan nato sa atong materials.”

(Also, we were assigned to create and provide materials used in teaching. Then we were just dependent on the soft copies of the teaching materials in formal education. We will just focus on formal education and what modules will be used per quarter since we do not have a direct person who can provide educational materials.)

➤ *Insufficiency of Teachers for ALS – SHS*

One of the major lived experiences of the participants in this study is facing problems because of a lack of teachers for ALS – SHS. As per the participants, they encountered problems in implementing the ALS-SHS program because of a disproportionate number of available teachers who should have handled subjects in ALS – SHS. Then another matter that caused problems for ALS-SHS is having lack of teachers who specializes in skills training for ALS – SHS. In this light, participants were being challenged with the lack of well-trained teachers who should conduct instructions for ALS – SHS.

- *In line with this notion, IDI-02 stressed that:*
“Kulang kaayu ang teachers nato nga...daghan kaayug subject, 22 ka subjects, 23 then pila lang ang teachers nga nagtudlo ato.”

(We lack teachers because we have 22 to 23 subjects then there are only a few teachers teaching the subjects.)

- *IDI-03 also explained that:*
“First are the teachers, we are lacking teachers who have specialized subjects since it is very hard for us specifically those teachers who have who is a graduate of elementary education to be in the senior. Senior High program of alternative learning.”
- *Further, IDI-02 added that:*
“In terms of managing or implementing the ALS senior high, more challenging because the (lack of) well-trained teachers to conduct the instructions.”

In managing the implementation of ALS Senior High School, the participants shared various difficulties and adjustments in teaching ALS – SHS. They also narrated the unavailability of curriculum guide and LIS intended for ALS – SHS and their difficulties in producing modules and teaching materials, and lack of teachers for ALS – SHS.

B. Coping Strategies of the ALS Mobile Teachers on the Challenges Encountered in ALS Senior High School Implementation

By comprehensive perusal of the answers of research participants in connection to their employed strategies to cope with the challenges faced in ALS senior high school implementation, there were four (4) themes developed: 1) asking and receiving assistance from stakeholders; 2) researching and studying; 3) using other strategies to solve problems, and 4) managing time.

Table 2 shows the major themes and core ideas on the coping strategies of the ALS mobile teachers on the encountered problems in managing the ALS senior high school implementation.

Table 2 Major Themes and Core Ideas on the Coping Strategies of the ALS Mobile Teachers on the Challenges Encountered in ALS Senior High School Implementation

Major Themes	Core Ideas
Asking and Receiving Assistance from Stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seeking help from ALS supervisor and receiving technical assistance from the school principal and teachers • Asking help from the teachers in the formal education about the Learner Information System (LIS) • Being helped by the DepEd through having class observations, lab sessions, and individual coaching • Tapping the LGU, barangay, DepEd personnel, and NGOs to get help in the implementation of the program • Receiving budgets and printing materials from non-government organizations (NGOs) and barangay officials • Asking for help to address the needs of the program through coordinating with the stakeholders in the community learning centre

Researching and Studying	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researching contents for modules to provide necessary lessons to learners • Studying the subjects assigned for them to teach specifically those that are not aligned to their specializations • Studying subjects and contents that require skills and hands-on demonstration
Using Other Strategies to Solve Problems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Staying positive by using own skills and experiences as a strategy to cope with the challenges • Distributing online digital modules to ease problems in printing and in transportation • Using personal supplies in printing materials • Coping easily with the problem because of getting used to it
Managing Time	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organizing one’s time to manage overlapping of teaching schedules • Dividing own schedule in teaching in ALS – SHS and in performing other ancillary tasks • Managing time to accommodate regular ALS class and ALS-SHS

➤ *Asking and Receiving Assistance from Stakeholders*

One of the major strategies employed by the participants to cope with the challenges encountered in ALS senior high school implementation was asking for and receiving assistance from stakeholders. The participants shared that they sought help and received technical assistance from the ALS supervisors, DepEd personnel, DepEd officials, and DepEd top management. As such, they received various assistance and aid from the LGU, non-government organizations (NGOs), and barangay officials. On the other hand, participants shared that they had coordinated with the stakeholders in the community learning center for the implementation of the ALS-SHS.

- *In connection with this strategy, FGD-01 humbly shared that:*

“First, I seek help from our Division ALS Supervisor. Number one, I asked for technical assistance, suggestions, and help since we could not do it on our own. Also, in our schools, the school principals extend their help, as well as the senior high school teachers in formal education. So, their extended assistance is a huge help to cope with these challenges, since having those suggestions and technical assistance, the problems are slowly resolved.”

- *IDI-01 also added that:*

“We cope with the challenges by always asking our head supervisor. And also, our master teacher or head teacher here in our mother school, and also our co-teachers or for co-ALS senior high school teachers. We ask them for advice, suggestion, and help because they are, the more knowledgeable in this implementation.”

- *Likewise, IDI-02 expressed that:*

“Also, with the help of my colleagues, they are eager to share their skills and knowledge.”

- *Further, IDI-01 stated that:*

“For me, it is really our EPS who provides technical assistance since we easily receive our needs.”

- *On the other hand, FGD-05 shared that they sought assistance from the formal system as regards the needed modules for ALS – SHS:*

“So, we have to seek assistance from the formal system noh, from the formal school. Asa mi manguha ug modules. Thankful mi kay they give all their... gihatag sa amoa tanan ang among mga panginahanglanon. So that’s why the Senior High School has successfully implemented.”

(So, we seek assistance from the formal system or formal school to get modules. We are thankful for them since they provided all their needs. So that is why the Senior High School has successfully implemented.)

- *FGD-04 then supported the statement:*

“Then ang katung mga reproduction of modules naga pangayo jud mig tabang or labi na sa mother School, kay sila man ang naay mga modules na or naa pud sa Deped Commons”

(On problems on modules reproduction, we ask help to our mother schools since they have access on the DepEd Commons.)

- *FGD-03 also expressed that asking for help from the teachers in the formal education about the Learner Information System (LIS) is one way to cope with the problems.*

“Then one of the challenges for this... sa LIS pud is medyo lahi ang LIS, sa atoa sa ALS, lahi pud ang pagka kuan...so na cope up namo...nag kuan lang gud mi... nag ask mig help, from the formal system. So ang mga challenges namo is na cope up lang gihapun namo, because we cooperate, we coordinate with others.”

(Then, one of the challenges for this is the LIS for ALS-SHS. We ask for help and assistance from the teachers in the formal education since we have different LIS. So, we cope with the challenges by fostering coordination and cooperation with others.)

- *Moreover, FGD-06 revealed that they received help from DepEd through class observations, lab sessions, and individual coaching:*

“So, with the help that the DepEd officials provided to overcome difficulties in managing the implementation of ALS senior high schools, we sought help. Especially when it comes to technical assistance..., these assistances were provided by them, especially through classroom observation, learning options, or lab sessions, or also these individual coaching. These three areas really help us, teachers, as mobile teachers do, strengthen and improve to address the diversity of our learners.”

- *Similarly, tapping the LGU, barangay, DepEd personnel, and NGOs was the employed strategy of IDI-03 to get help in the implementation of the program:*

“We come up with that particular problem by tapping the LGU local government unit and barangay kagawad and...also the Deped personnel, and not only the Deped personnel but also the, then non-government organizations such as the Rotary Golden Laces. We actually ask for support so that we can implement the program properly.”

- *FGD-02 also added that:*

“So ito talaga maganda dito that we are seeking help not only in the local government unit, but also in the ano... sa school mismo. Kasi, if ever kasi si ALS wala sa.. wala sa school then ALS senior high school I mean wala mismo sa school, then the budget would be ano.. difficult. So ito yung strategy na ito is itong pagkakaroon na natin ng connection sa teachers not just between the school but also in the barangay, ito talaga yung maganda when it comes to serving ALS.”

(So, this is wonderful that we can seek help not only in the local government but also in the school. Since if ever the ALS program itself does not have the budget, it would be difficult. So, this strategy has a connection with teachers not just in the school but also in the barangay. So, this really makes it wonderful when it comes to serving ALS.)

- *FGD-07 then shared that ALS received budgets and printing materials from non-government organizations (NGOs) and barangay officials:*

“Aside from the budget from the National meron din tayong nakuha na mga help from the non-government organizations. Yung iba pang government organization so nagbigay sila ng tulong sa ALS Senior High School in terms of like papers and other materials na kakailanganin ng mga learners namin di lang sa mga non-government organization but pati na din doon yung mga barangay officials.”

(Aside from the budget from the National Level, we also received help from non-government organizations. Other government organizations helped the ALS Senior High School program in terms of papers and other materials needed by the learners. Not just the non-government organizations but also the barangay officials.)

- *Similarly, IDI-01 uttered that:*

“They always provide us with supplies po. Kuntahay mangayo mig, for example when we ask for bondpaper or ink, or some barangay, barangay hall, they also provide printed modules.”

(They always provide us with supplies if ever we ask for bond paper or ink. In some barangay, they also provide printed modules.)

- *In support, IDI-03 simplified that:*

“I have received a ream of bond papers as well as printers. Since we have a scarcity of bank papers, stakeholders provided a bunch of bond papers so that we can help in bringing the modules. They also provided inks for a specific printer that we had.”

- *Furthermore, IDI-01 added that as ALS implementers, they asked for help to address the needs of the program by coordinating with the stakeholders in the community learning center:*

“In addition to that is the stakeholders in the community Learning Center, like the barangay, so kung naa mi kailangan, muduol jud mi, mangutana mi unsa pwede nilang matabang.”

(In addition to that is the stakeholders in the community Learning Center like the barangay officials. So, if we need something, we just approach them, or we ask them if what help they can extend.)

- *Then, IDI-02 also shared that:*

“Siguro kato ra mang mga materials and moral support ra man siguro, materials katung mga bondpaper man lang siguro gikan sa, ang stakeholder lang siguro is the school. Makahatag ato provides also the building nga gigamit nato. So mao to sya... basta naay structure makita sa learners nga naay structure ug ang structure then naa puy mga materials.”

(Maybe, the materials and moral support. The stakeholders provide us with materials like bond paper for the school. The school provided a building for the classes. It is important that learners will see the structures and then the materials.)

➤ *Researching and Studying*

For the participants, researching and studying was a big help to cope with the challenges faced in the implementation of the ALS senior high school program. As shared by them, they have researched contents for modules to provide necessary lessons to ALS- SHS learners. Also, they were studying the subjects assigned for them to teach, specifically those that were not aligned with their specializations. As such, they were studying the subjects and contents that require skills and hands-on demonstration.

- *In line with this generated theme, FGD-04 declared that:*

“Naga research pud mi, para lang gyud mahatag namo ang mga modules, nga dapat namo nga mahatag sa mga learners po.”

(Also, we are searching for topics so that we can provide the right modules to our learners.)

- *In addition, FGD-05 clarified that:*

“Study first before we teach.”

- *Similarly, FGD-01 shared that they studied the subjects assigned for them to teach, specifically those that are not aligned to their specializations:*

“We need to study talaga our specific subject. It's because kasi kailangan talaga naming magturo, kasi we are not, among tawag dyan, mao na among focus nga mga subject like gi mentioned...kanina about sa Math, di naman sya Math major.”

(We really need to study our specific subject. It is because we really need to teach, as we are not experts on the subject like as mentioned earlier about math, but they are not Math majors.)

- *Furthermore, FGD-04 added that studying subjects and content that require skills and hands-on demonstration is a huge help for them:*

“Gamiton jud diay nato ang atong brain, kay syempre, dili man pud ta makahatag sa ilaha ug pagtudlo kung dili pud ta mag-study. So, dapat mag-study gyud ta, parehas sa level-up sa senior high, dili basta-basta kay more on hands on.”

(So, it is important to use our brains since we cannot share learning if we do not study the lessons. So, we must study our lessons since it is important to level up our learnings because ALS-SHS is more hands-on.)

- *IDI-02 also stressed that:*

“How should you choose a research problem or topic to be studied? Expound your answers well.”

➤ *Using Other Strategies to Solve Problems*

In managing the implementation of ALS - SHS, the participants used other strategies to solve problems met. They ensured to stay positive by using their own skills and experiences as a strategy to cope with the challenges. As such, they were distributing online digital modules to ease problems in printing and in transportation. They also revealed that they used their personal supplies in printing materials. On the other hand, they coped easily with the problem because of getting used to it.

- *In support of this notion, IDI-02 disclosed that:*

“So, stay positive lang, mao to akong giingun nga... based on my, based on our skills, teachers, although kami tanan is naa man gyud skills and knowledge and background for all the subjects we have, so ang akoang personal strategy is gamit lang nako ang how I teach my previous Junior High's High School.”

(So, just stay positive. As teachers, we have our skills, knowledge, and background for all subjects. So, I just also used my personal strategy in my previous Junior High School class.)

- *FGD-03 also shared that they were distributing online digital modules to ease problems in printing and in transportation:*

“For me, first, one coping strategy is we give digital modules to students who cannot actively report to the school, just like during online classes.”

- *FGD-04 then added that:*

“In coping that problem, ang ginabuhat namo, nagahatag nalang mi ug digital module.”

(In coping that problem, we provided digital modules.)

- *Moreover, IDI-02 expressed that they used their personal supplies in printing materials:*

“So katung mga difficulties so they say difficulties katung sa materials, so dali nalang man gyud to kay kami naman ang mo-provide ug print, naa may printer pud nga personal gigamit.”

(So, for the difficulties on materials, we easily provide those since we are the ones who printed the materials because we have our own printer.)

- *Furthermore, FGD-01 revealed that they easily cope with the problem because of getting used to it:
“When we talk about coping mechanisms, a mobile teacher, actually we are used to how to cope since every now and then we are facing different problems.”*

➤ *Managing Time*

As shared by the participants, they made sure to have time management for them to have a smooth implementation of the ALS-SHS program. They organized one’s time to manage overlapping teaching schedules. Also, they divided their schedule between teaching in ALS – SHS and in performing other ancillary functions. More so, they ensured to manage their time to managing time to accommodate regular ALS classes and ALS-SHS.

- *In linking to this extracted theme, FGD-06 spoke about organizing one’s time to manage overlapping teaching schedules:
“I’d like to elaborate more on the organization. Of course, I am not just a senior high school teacher alone. So, we have a lot of implementers that just meet so we are organizing our time on how to manage it properly so that there will be no overlapping between us teachers. And of course, like we can facilitate right on time, and just like what I have said there will be no overlapping and respecting it’s time for each subject that we are teaching.”*
- *FGD-02 then supported the statement of FGD-06:
“Yung number one natin it's the time management natin.”*

(Our number one is really time management.)

- *Moreover, FGD-05 shared about dividing their own schedule in teaching in ALS – SHS and performing other ancillary tasks:
“So, I have to divide my schedule. Since I have a class. I am a designated EPSA then I have to teach the senior high school. So instead of working from home, I have to go to ALS senior high school the other work from home, so I have only one work from home. So, I gave my... full-time support to ALS senior high school every Friday... I have to manage my time because for... para sa bayan para sa bata, sabi nila noh.”*

(So, I have to divide my schedule. Since I have a class. I am a designated EPSA, then I must teach the senior high school. So instead of working from home, I must go with ALS senior high school the other work from home, so I have only one work from home. So, I gave my full-time support to ALS senior high school every Friday. I must manage my time because we are doing it for the country and for the children, as they say.)

- *On the other hand, FGD-03 unveiled that managing time to accommodate regular ALS classes and ALS-SHS is another way of coping with the problems:
“So it is, mag-manage jud kag time for your regular ALS class and your ALS senior high.”*

(So, you need to manage your time for your regular ALS class and your ALS senior high.)

Despite the challenges in ALS senior high school implementation, the participants employed strategies to cope with the challenges they faced through asking and receiving assistance from stakeholders. They also do research and studying. Also, they were using other strategies to solve problems. Nevertheless, having a good time management really works in solving some of their problems.

C. Insights Drawn from The Experiences of Mobile Teachers in the Implementation of ALS Senior High School

By careful assessment of the answers of participants in connection to their insights drawn from their experiences in managing the implementation of ALS Senior High School, five (5) themes were found: 1) positive outlook of becoming an ALS – SHS Mobile Teacher; 2) professional growth and personal gains; 3) provision of additional budget, training, and teachers for ALS – SHS Program; 4) assessment and monitoring of the ALS – SHS Program, and 5) designing of specific curriculum for ALS – SHS.

Table 3 presents the distinct insights of the mobile teachers drawn from their experiences in managing the implementation of ALS Senior High School.

Table 3 Major Themes and Core Ideas on the Insights Drawn from the Experiences of Mobile Teachers in the Implementation of ALS Senior High School

Major Themes	Core Ideas
Positive Outlook as an ALS – SHS Mobile Teacher	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experience excitement in teaching unfamiliar strands and lessons • Have fulfillment in gaining skills and knowledge and being able to share it with als – shs learners • Be inspired with co – als mobile teachers by seeing the strength of each teacher • Become more capable and tough in teaching different levels of students as an als teacher • Believe in one’s capability to overcome the challenges in implementing and adjusting to the als – shs • Never doubt and limit oneself as a teacher • Become resourceful in looking for ways to provide materials in the implementation of als – shs • Be flexible to attain goals in the implementation of als – shs • Reflect on your own teaching capability • Be helpful and motivator for learners of als – shs to continue their studies and to achieve their dreams
Professional Growth and Personal Gains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grow personally and professionally through studying specific subjects • Gain more knowledge in implementing als – shs especially on the hands-on skills training • Acquire more knowledge through studying and equipping oneself with the contents of specific subjects • Be able to amplify one’s knowledge on the subjects being handled to share additional inputs to als – shs learners • Increase tesda national certificates on specific skills through the implementation of als – shs • Make the national certificates gained from the implementation of als – shs as an opportunity for promotion • Learn new skills to be shared to learners and for future purposes as a teacher • Continue to gain more knowledge in teaching the learners • Maintain the exercise of one’s teaching specialization in teaching a particular strand in als – shs
Provision of Additional Budget, Trainings, and Teachers for ALS – SHS Program	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide more budget for equipment and training in the implementation of ALS – SHS • Conduct more training for ALS – SHS mobile teachers to improve the teaching-learning process • Give additional compensation and allowance to ALS mobile teachers considering that they are handling multi-grade level • Hire additional teachers specifically those who have specializations aligned for SHS-ALS
Assessment and Monitoring of the ALS – SHS Program	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustain the assessment and monitoring of the needs of the ALS – SHS program • Supervise the program as heads or principals to look for ways how to give assistance so the program may continually grow • Conduct an evaluation on the alignment of activities of the program implementation of ALS – SHS
Designing of Specific Curriculum for ALS – SHS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specific curriculum intended for ALS – SHS • Create its own curriculum to answer the quarterly capacities and needs of the learners • Formulate a curriculum for ALS – SHS to lessen the difficulties in its implementation that the current curriculum brings to learners

➤ *Positive Outlook of Becoming an ALS – SHS Mobile Teacher*

One of the insights of participants in relation to their experiences is having positive outlook of becoming an ALS – SHS mobile teacher. They experienced excitement and fulfillment in implementing the ALS-SHS program. Also, they were inspired as they became more capable and tough in teaching different levels of students. As such, they were able to become resourceful and flexible to attain goals in the implementation of ALS – SHS. Moreover, they were able to reflect on their own teaching capability. With this, they were able to believe in their capability to overcome the challenges in implementing and adjusting to the ALS – SHS. More so, they were becoming helpful motivators for learners of ALS – SHS to continue their studies and achieve their dreams.

- *In connection to this collected insight, IDI-01 shared that they are experiencing excitement in teaching unfamiliar strands and lessons:*

“Experience... Excited, exciting pud sya, it's because we knew amoang lesson na i-discuss, kaning foreign kaayu sa amoa ang subjects, ang mga strands, so ma-excite pud mi, na maka-learn mi, then maka-impart pud mi sa mga bata.”

(We experience excitement because we knew that with the lessons we were discussing, the lessons or strands were also foreign to us. That is why it is exciting for us since we will be able to learn, and we can impart learning to the learners.)

- *In addition, IDI-02 shared about having fulfillment in gaining skills and knowledge and being able to share it with ALS – SHS learners:*

“Fulfillment man, all teachers for the implementation of the... for this study all teachers are...naa silay, we have national certificate for the skills nga among i-share. So murag kuan sa amoa nga nga mi mga knowledge and skills, nga i-share namo sa mga ALS teachers, ALS students sa senior high. Kato sya nga experience is more, murag ma-fulfill, nga ang amoang skills is ma-share sa ALS Senior High learners.”

(It is also fulfilling since all the teachers involved in the implementation received a national certificate for the skills we share in class. For us, we were able to share knowledge with ALS teachers and learners. Those experiences somewhat fulfilling since we can share our skills with ALS- SHS learners.)

- *FGD-01 also stressed that they are being inspired with co – ALS mobile teachers through seeing the strength of each teacher:*
“So, suggestions to my co-mobile teachers, actually... padayun lang, and laban pa rin. I am so, kuan naman din, inspired with all my co mobile teachers. It's really difficult and I see the strength of each one of us, but suggestions, laban lang gihapun ta.”

(So, suggestions to my co-mobile teachers, go on and keep on fighting. Since I am so also inspired by all my co-mobile teachers. I know it is difficult, so keep on fighting since I see the strength of each one of us.)

- *Moreover, IDI-01 added that they are becoming more capable and tough in teaching different levels of students as an ALS teacher:*

“I realized that we become jack of all trades because we teach BLP, we teach elementary, we teach junior high school, and now we are also teaching senior high school... It will make us better and tougher talaga. Na in dealing in dealing this new implementation sa ALS senior high. So senior high school so, kaning ang epekto sa amoa, kay kato... maging jack of all trades gyud mi ALS teacher because of that”

(I realized that we had become a jack of all trades because we teach BLP, elementary, and junior high school levels, and now we are also teaching senior high school. Dealing with this new implementation in ALS senior high will make us better and tougher. So, the effect of senior high school so, we became a jack of all trades ALS teacher because of that)

- *As such, IDI-01 added another detailed insight into which they believe in one’s capability to overcome the challenges in implementing and adjusting to the ALS – SHS:*

“Kanang, kaya nato ni. It's just hard in the beginning or in the start, but as time goes on, I know this implementation will never no never end, tuloy-tuloy na jud ni, so we have to adjust na lang jud to the continuing ano, progress sa ALS system na naa nay senior high.”

(We can do it. It is just hard in the beginning or at the start, but as time goes on, I know this implementation will never end since it will continue. So, we must adjust to the continuing progress in the ALS system, specifically in the senior high school program.)

- *Furthermore, FGD-02 clarified that they never doubted and limit themselves as a teacher:*

“It comes to your teaching profession, never doubt yourself and then do not limit yourself. Kasi as a teacher we are teaching a multi grade. So, imagine from teaching a basic literacy program up to the Senior High School. So, ito talaga, do not limit yourself in learning. Set always as a good example to your co teacher, kasi hindi madali yung trabaho and some talaga, sa profession natin some talaga madali ma-drain.”

(When it comes to your teaching profession, never doubt yourself and do not limit yourself in learning. Since, as a teacher, we are teaching multi-grade, but ALS is often a multi-level teacher. So, imagine teaching a basic literacy program up to the Senior High School program. So, that is it, do not limit yourself to learning. Set yourself as a good example to your co-teacher because our profession is not easy; in our profession, some of us are drained easily.)

- *Besides, IDI-02 disclosed that they are becoming resourceful in looking for ways to provide materials in the implementation of ALS – SHS:*

“Another is positive is mahimong kuan pud ang teacher, resourceful, na mangita syag paraan na to provide those materials or supplemental materials for the implementation of the ALS senior high.”

(Another is positive, teachers will become resourceful since they find ways to provide supplemental material for the implementation of the ALS senior high school.)

- *In fact, IDI-03 explained that they are becoming flexible to attain goals in the implementation of ALS – SHS:*
“Because of these experiences, we can learn our teachers learn how to be flexible enough in order for us to attain or achieve our goals in the implementation of ALS senior high school.”

- *And then IDI-03 added that they are being able to reflect on their own teaching capability:*
“Siguro personally, this will help me or makita sa akoa how I will deal with the ALS learners kung capable ba ko or dili, so kung angayan ba gyud ko mo-teach ani nga mga learners.”

(Maybe, personally, this will help me to see myself if I can teach the learners.)

- *On the other hand, FGD-06 stated that they are becoming helpful and motivator for learners of ALS – SHS to continue their studies and achieve their dreams:*

“I believe the insight that can be drawn from the experiences of mobile teachers, in the implementation of senior high school is that we as a mobile teacher, we became motivator ta sa atoang mga learner. Since we will help them develop their skills, they will become motivated in continuing their school kasi after the junior high school, pwede naman silang magtrabaho eh because sa ilahang mga edad. But then, as senior high school teacher, we also motivate them to continue their studies, of course.”

(I believe the insight that can be drawn from the experiences of mobile teachers in the implementation of senior high school is that we, mobile teachers, we became motivators of our learners. Since we help them develop their skills, through that, they will become motivated to continue their school. After finishing junior high school, they can easily find a job because of their age. But then, as senior high school teachers, we also motivate them to continue their studies.)

- *Further, FGD-01 supported the notion of FGD-06:*

“Ang opportunity ug insights pud nako ana, we can, having this implementation, nakatabang pud mi sa among mga learners jud na to achieve their dreams pud na to graduate senior high and to proceed in college.”

(With my opportunity and insights on having this implementation, we were able to help our learners to achieve their dreams by helping them to graduate senior high, so that they can also proceed in college.)

➤ *Professional Growth and Personal Gains*

Another insight of participants drawn from their experiences in implementing the ALS-SHS is having professional growth and personal gains. As shared by them, they were able to grow personally and professionally through studying specific subjects and teaching higher levels of education in ALS – SHS. As such, they were able to equip themselves with new learnings and skills. In this light, they were able to amplify one’s knowledge of the subjects being handled to share additional inputs to ALS – SHS learners. Ultimately, they gained TESDA national certificates and other national certificates on specific skills through the implementation of ALS – SHS as an opportunity for promotion.

- *As a proof of this generated theme, FGD-01 stated that they grow personally and professionally through studying specific subjects:*

“It really helped us mobile teacher to grow personally and professionally. So, we are mobile teachers knowing that we mentioned a while ago, kanina with all the teachers that they mentioned, na talaga we are we need to study talaga our specific subject.”

(It really helped us, mobile teachers, to grow personally and professionally. So, we are mobile teachers, knowing that we mentioned a while ago that we needed to study our specific subject.)

- *Then, IDI-01 added that:*

“We gain personal growth and development pud.”

(We also gain personal growth and development.)

- *Besides, FGD-03 spoke that they are being able to grow professionally by experiencing teaching higher level of education in ALS – SHS:*

“For me is...my insights are the experience itself on teaching senior ALS senior high school. Because for me, it is a good experience for me, for me to grow professionally. Ma experience pud nako ang pagtudlo in the higher level of education for the ALS learners.”

(For me, my insights are the experience of teaching senior ALS senior high school itself. Because for me, it is a good experience for me to grow professionally. I was able to experience teaching at a higher level of education for ALS learners.)

- *In addition, FGD-04 shared about gaining more knowledge in implementing ALS – SHS, especially on the hands-on skills training:*

“My insight about my experience in teaching or implementing ALS senior high school is that I gain knowledge. So dapat talaga gamitun jud diay nato ang atong brain, kay syempre, dili man pud ta makahatag sa ilaha ug pagtudlo kung dili pud ta mag-study. So, dapat mag-study gyud ta, parehas sa level-up sa senior high, dili basta-basta kay more on hands on.”

(My insight about my experience in teaching or implementing ALS senior high school is that I gain knowledge. So, it is important to use our brains since we cannot share learning if we do not study the lessons. So, we must study our lessons since it is important to level up our learnings because ALS-SHS is more hands on.)

- *Similarly, IDI-01 expressed that they gain more knowledge through studying and equipping themselves with the contents of specific subjects:*

“Desirable experiences, kana jung we gain more knowledge gyud. Because Junior High secondary teacher or junior high school teacher and then this all the subjects all the subjects are same man gud...and then and then for us we have to be equipped. So we need to learn, para ma-impart gyud nato, matudlo pud nato atong nahibal-an. So continuing learning gyud gihapon sya.”

(We have desirable experiences as we gain more knowledge because junior high school teacher and then this all the subjects are the same. Then for us to be equipped, we need to learn the subjects to impart learnings to learners. With that, we have continuing learning.)

- *In addition, FGD-07 shared the same insight:*

“My desirable desirable experience as the implement as to the implementation of ALS senior high school... mas ma eager pa ko na magtuon sa akong lesson kay mas lahi man gud sya sa way na atung gina tudlo sa elementary ug secondary nato sa alternative learning system kay ang kaning Senior High School nato nag base man gud to sa formal na curriculum.. So, in teaching sa mga lesson, so mas different sya nga lessons sa atuang mga learners from secondary and elementary, so dapat jud natong matun-an ug maayo”

(My desirable experience as to the implementation of ALS senior high school is that we are eager to study the lessons since we have different teaching strategies in ALS-elementary and secondary levels. So, for ALS-SHS, we based the curriculum on the SHS formal education, that is why we have different ways of teaching the learners. So, in teaching the lesson, it is different lessons for learners from secondary and elementary, so that is why it is necessary to learn it comprehensively.)

- *More so, FGD-05 shared a similar point:*

“We got a lot of opportunities and learnings because as we go on with our subjects, each one of us has different subjects fit to our capacity to teach the senior high school learners. So, we are also thankful for the opportunity given to us because we will learn a lot, as long as... along the way, we learn a lot. And we also know our limitations in... in managing the senior high school program.”

(We got a lot of opportunities and learnings as we went on with our subjects. Each one of us was assigned different subjects that fit our capacity in teaching senior high school learners. So, we are also thankful for the opportunity given to us because we learn a lot. And we also know our limitations in managing the senior high school program.)

- *On the other hand, FGD-03 disclosed that they are being able to amplify one’s knowledge on the subjects being handled to share other inputs to ALS – SHS learners:*

“Mas ni level up ang ilahang mga lessons or ang pagtudlo pud namo so ingun ana pud ang... tama tama pud ang pagbahin or sa paghati-hati sa mga subjects, sa among mga teachers.. which is hiyang sa amoa among subjects...which is desirable nga experience para sa akua ug ma amplify pa namo ang amoang knowledge ato nga subject or madungagan amoang ma input para sa mga students.”

(Their lessons are leveled-up subjects and the same with our teachings. Also, we teachers were able to choose the subjects which we considered our expertise. Also, another desirable experience is that we were able to amplify our knowledge, and with that, we were able to acquire new inputs for our students.)

- *Furthermore, IDI-02 exposed that they are gaining TESDA national certificates on specific skills through the implementation of ALS – SHS:*

“In the implementation of ALS senior high. So of course, we gained certificates from that and that is considered as opportunities when it comes to... sa promotion. Since I am a (TESDA) national certificate holder of one skill noh, so I am also open for another training to gain lots of certificate because I am aiming not just one skill. So, the more na daghan ta ug certificate the more opportunities that will be given.”

(In the implementation of ALS senior high school, we gained certificates, which are considered opportunities for promotion. Since I am a (TESDA) national certificate holder that specializes in one skill, so I am also open to other training to gain lots of certificates because I am aiming not just one skill. So, the more certificate, the more opportunities that will be given.)

- *In fact, IDI-03 agreed with this by sharing that getting the national certificates gained from the implementation of ALS – SHS is an opportunity for promotion:*

“The opportunities that I have gained, we can actually use the NC II that we get before we apply it in the DepEd.”

- *This is also supported by IDI-01:*

“Isa gyud diha is the promotion. Some of my co-mobile teachers, or ALS teacher, were already promoted”

(One of those is gaining promotion. Some of my co-mobile teachers, or ALS teachers, were already promoted.)

➤ *Provision of Additional Budget, Trainings, and Teachers for ALS – SHS Program*

Provision of added budget, training, and teachers for ALS – SHS program is one of the insights of participants drawn from their experiences in implementing the ALS-SHS. As for the participants, they must be provided with more budget for equipment and training in the implementation of ALS – SHS. As such, they must receive more seminars and training to improve the teaching-learning process. On the other hand, they shared that they must be given added compensation and allowance considering that they are handling multi-grade levels. Eventually, they shared that there must be hiring of more teachers, specifically those who have specializations aligned with the SHS-ALS program.

- *In line with this notion, IDI-02 expressed that they must be provided more budget for equipment and training in the implementation of ALS – SHS:*

“They must provide more attention on providing the equipment, training and the budget for the implementation of the ALS senior the high. So kinahanglan jud siya.”

(They must provide more attention to providing the equipment, training, and the budget for the implementation of the ALS senior high. So, it is really needed.)

- *Similarly, FGD-02 added that:*

“We have also sought budget specifically for the implementation of ALS Senior High School. So dapat the more budget nga naa para kay ALS, the more nah dagko ang ma-offer ni ALS for the learners.”

(We have also sought a budget specifically for the implementation of ALS Senior High School. So, we should have more budget for ALS so that we can offer more opportunities for the learners.)

- *On the other hand, FGD-02 voiced that there must be more seminars and training for ALS – SHS mobile teachers to improve the teaching-learning process:*

“My suggestion lang ito, seminars and trainings for the improvement of the teaching and learning process. Seminar for the and trainings for the teachers.”

(My suggestion is training and seminars for the improvement of the teaching and learning process. Seminar and training for the teachers.)

- *And this was supported by IDI-01:*

“If they will choose us to teach, dapat we should undergo trainings gyud.”

(If they will choose us to teach, we should undergo trainings.)

- *More so, IDI-03 stated that there must be giving of more compensation and allowance for ALS mobile teachers considering that they are handling multi-grade levels:*

“I highly suggest they need to compensate for additional compensation for the teachers. So, we are handling three programs, elementary, junior high school and the senior high school because in ALS, we're not only handling one level of learners, but we are handling multi grade. So, if they will do that, I highly suggest they will compensate the teacher or provide allowance, let's just say traveling allowance, that can compensate the teacher.”

- *In fact, FGD-01 have the same insight with IDI-03:*

“Actually, we would also like to have additional compensation if pwede. Because hindi kasi ito madali. We are kuan naman din, being honest. Other programs naa may compensations bisan nagtudlo na sa formal, then naa pay additional na allowance? So, I think kailangan ng mga mobile teachers senior high school teacher ng additional allowance naman din.”

(Actually, we would also like to have additional compensation if possible. We are being honest; our work is not easy. Other programs have compensations even if they are teaching in formal education with additional allowance. So, I think mobile teachers in the senior high school program need an additional allowance.)

- Furthermore, IDI-03 asserted that there must be hiring of added teachers, specifically those who have specializations aligned for SHS-ALS:

“The management strategies that I can recommend... They need to, for the DepEd, they need to hire teachers that is fitted in this particular program, those teachers that has the capacity. I'm not saying that the mobile teachers doesn't have any capacity, but I'm talking about the teachers who has a specialized subject or major subject to be in this particular program, because as I said earlier, it is very hard for elementary teachers to handle Senior High School, since the curriculum guide they had in the elementary, and the curriculum guide that we had in ALS senior high school is very different.”

- Besides, IDI-01 expressed the same insight about hiring more teachers:
“This one I would really want to suggest or recommend to Deped, that they should hire ALS senior high teachers to teach ALS students.”

Moreover, as shared by participants, they must keep on learning new skills to be shared with learners and for future purposes as a teacher. More so, the participants shared that there must be keeping the exercise of one's teaching specialization in teaching a particular strand in ALS – SHS.

- In the context of this insight, IDI-02 spoke that they must keep on learning new skills to be shared with learners and for future purposes as a teacher:

“We will keep learning new skills. Kay ang sa kuan man gud, ang sa senior high more on the, ang katung gi kuan man gud, more on the...skills track. So, we keep learning skills kay para ma-share pud nato sa other, sa atung learners. We keep learning another or new skills para magamit pud nato, in the future, if we are planning to teach senior high, Senior High either in the ALS, or in the formal.”

(We will keep learning new skills. Since the ALS-SHS is on a different level, it focuses on the skills track. So, we keep learning skills so that we can share them with the learners. We keep learning other or new skills so that they can be used in the future, if we are planning to teach senior high in the ALS or in the formal.)

- In addition, FGD-07 stated that continuing of gaining more knowledge is important in teaching the learners:
“So, continue lang ta, gaining more knowledge in teaching our learners.”

(So, we just continue gaining more knowledge in teaching our learners.)

- And then, FGD-01 supported the insight of FGD-07:
“Then continue to have to gain knowledge.”

- Likewise, IDI-03 expressed that there must be maintaining exercise of one's teaching specialization in teaching a particular strand in ALS – SHS:

“The opportunities, the opportunities that we have gained, in the implementation of ALS senior high school is that teachers in alternative learning system who has this special subject or a specialized subject or a major because they can actually exercise it in this particular strand.”

➤ Assessment and Monitoring of the ALS – SHS Program

In analyzing this study, it was found that one of the major insights of the participants in relation to their experiences in implementing the ALS-SHS is the assessment and monitoring of the ALS – SHS program. As shared by them, there must be sustained assessment and monitoring of the needs of the ALS – SHS program. Also, they shared that there must be supervision of the program to look for ways how to give help so the program may continually grow. Moreover, for them, an evaluation of the alignment of activities of the program implementation of ALS – SHS must be conducted.

- In line with this common insight, IDI-03 stated that sustained assessment and monitoring of the needs of the ALS – SHS program must be done:

“The best approaches and practices of our supervisors is that they will take note of what is the problem, or what are the lacking in this particular program so that they can assess it and then find ways to provide those things that is very needed in this particular program, which is the alternative learning, Senior High School in alternative learning system. They can tap the central office or the ALS central office, or the DepEd, or the support that we need in this particular program.”

- *In addition, IDI-02 shared that there must be supervision of the program to look for ways how to give aid so the program may continually grow:*

“Ma-advice or ma-share is the supervisors, or the heads of the ALS must take a look on giving assistance. Also, same advice sa mga principal para ang program is mo-grow. Take a look jud sila, ilang tanan buhaton by supervising all the program.”

(What I can share as an advice to the supervisors and heads of the ALS is that they must look to giving assistance. Also, the same advice for the principal so that the program will grow. They should look into everything they do by supervising all the programs.)

- *Besides, FGD-04 spoke that there must be conducted an evaluation on the alignment of activities of the program implementation of ALS – SHS:*

“As higher official or sa mga Deped official dapat ma-evaluate kung tama ba ang pagpa-kuan sa senior high school, unsay tawag ani, pagpa-implement, ug nagsubay ba gyud sya, sa tama nga formulation pud sa curriculum sa ALS senior high school.”

(So, as higher officials, they should have evaluated if the ALS-SHS is correctly implemented or on the right path based on the formulated curriculum of ALS senior high school.)

➤ *Designing of Specific Curriculum for ALS – SHS*

Designing of specific curriculum for ALS – SHS is another generated theme from the answers of participants. From the participants, there must be developed specific curriculum intended for the implementation of ALS – SHS. Also, they shared that there must be formulated curriculum for ALS – SHS to lessen the difficulties in its implementation and to ease the difficulties that the current curriculum brings to learners.

- *In line with this insight, FGD-02 expressed that developing a specific curriculum intended for ALS – SHS is needed:*

“ALS Senior High School should have its own curriculum not only based on the curriculum performance system, because honestly, when it comes to face to face, mahirap mag cope-up yung learner namin, it's because it's not really intended for a one day in a week class. The curriculum is intended for the entire week.”

(ALS Senior High School should have its own curriculum not only based on the curriculum performance system, because honestly, when it comes to face-to-face, the learner also could not be able to cope because the classes are not really intended for a one-day-in-a-week class. The curriculum is intended for the entire week.)

- *In fact, IDI-03 supported the notion of FGD-02:*

“The management strategies that I can recommend... they need to (have curriculum), for the DepEd... the curriculum guide they had in the elementary, and the curriculum guide that we had in ALS senior high school is very different.”

- *Furthermore, FGD-04 voiced that there must be formulated curriculum for ALS – SHS to lessen the difficulties in its implementation and to ease the difficulties that the current curriculum brings to learners:*

“The management strategy that I can recommend to the officials in the implementation of ALS seniors Senior High School is the formulation of the curriculum. As we all know, the ALS-SHS is only using the curriculum in the formal school, so they should have formulation in ALS Senior High School so that it would not be difficult for students. So, it should have formulated a curriculum in ALS Senior High School.”

- *Finally, FGD-03 uttered that there must be a formulated curriculum for ALS – SHS to cater to the learners' capacities and needs every grading period:*

“Hopefully, the management will create its own curriculum based on the needs and capacities of the learners suited for every designated grading periods.”

Though there were challenges that participants have encountered in managing the implementation of ALS Senior High School, they also have several realizations from their experiences such as having a positive outlook when becoming an ALS – SHS Mobile Teacher. They also shared about gaining professional growth and personal gains. On the other hand, they suggested for a provision of additional budget, training, and teachers for ALS – SHS Program and to have an assessment and monitoring of the program.

CHAPTER FIVE DISCUSSIONS

This chapter includes discussions that are based on the results of this phenomenological study and supported by academic research from experts in the field that was published in reputable, arbitrated publications as well as peer-reviewed journals. The implications for administrative practice, the recommendations for future research, and the researcher's closing remarks are also included in this chapter.

This study's primary objective is to find and examine the lived experiences of ALS mobile teachers in managing the implementation of ALS-SHS. Through using a methodical and ethical approach in conducting a focus group discussion and in-depth interviews, substantial data was collected. To completely capture the extensive data required for this investigation, all interviews were directed by a single validated interview guide. In addition, participants were chosen to submit comprehensive answers, which were then subjected to complex analysis with the assistance of research experts.

A. The Lived Experiences of Mobile Teachers Managing the Implementation of ALS Senior High School

By conducting Focus Group Discussion and In-Depth Interviews, the participants of this study who are ALS mobile teachers shared significant and relevant lived experiences in managing the implementation of ALS-SHS. Upon scrutinizing the answers of the participants, four (4) themes were acquired: 1) difficulties and adjustments in teaching ALS – SHS; 2) unavailability of curriculum guide and LIS intended for ALS – SHS; 3) difficulties in producing modules and teaching materials; and 4) insufficiency of teachers for ALS – SHS.

➤ *Difficulties and Adjustments in Teaching ALS – SHS*

One of the combined lived experiences of the participants is having difficulties and adjustments in teaching ALS – SHS. As shared by them, there are difficulties in teaching ALS – SHS because they lack proper skills training and orientation. As such, they were having a hard time adjusting since the implementation of ALS – SHS and its system are not yet fully prepared. Likewise, they were having big adjustments to the implementation of the program and its system, including the grading system. In addition, some of them specialize in different fields, which presents a challenge for them when teaching ALS - SHS adult learners. Due to the lack of face-to-face interaction and hands-on learning, they found it challenging to teach skills training to ALS - SHS TVL students.

In line with this theme, Odey and Opoh (2019) stated that the problem with different levels of education is not how policies are made, but how the Senior High School Curriculum is implemented. Despite large sums of money spent on implementing new curricula, a number of these attempts have failed. The main reason it did not work was that both outside and inside experts did not understand the school's culture. Teachers have a difficult time adjusting to their new jobs because they do not receive adequate training and orientation. To successfully implement curriculum, you must first understand how people in the school system share power, their traditions, and their roles and responsibilities.

Moreover, during the process of establishing the curriculum for senior high school, there were concerns over the lack of curricular faithfulness exhibited by the teachers. The need to understand potential obstacles that may impede instructors when they are required to implement a new curriculum for senior high school is the connection that makes identifying the concerns of teachers relevant to the current suggested study. By addressing these concerns both before and during the process of curriculum implementation, it will be possible to boost the success rate by providing administrators with the appropriate tools they need to help teachers as they go through changes in the curriculum (Arpilleda, 2018).

Further, the activities that take place in the classroom on a regular basis and in which the teacher participates to assess the student's level of achievement and track their development in the curriculum are referred to as "curriculum implementation." The newly implemented curriculum in senior high school is the responsibility of the teachers, and it is their job to evaluate whether it is having the desired effect on the students' academic performance or not. Teachers rely on the materials in the curriculum, the teaching approach, their own prior experiences, and their content knowledge of the curriculum to successfully do the tasks they have been given. The curriculum for senior high school must be taught by teachers who have sufficient knowledge and have received adequate training (Lynch & Mannion, 2021).

➤ *Unavailability of Curriculum Guide and LIS Intended for ALS – SHS*

Another issue identified by this study is the lack of curriculum guides and LIS designed for ALS - SHS. Due to the lack of a concrete curriculum for ALS - SHS, the ALS mobile teachers are temporarily using formal education curriculum. Furthermore, because there was no curriculum designed specifically for ALS in SHS, they had difficulty adapting formal education curriculum. As a result, they have been challenged in handling ALS for Senior High School because they are using formal education curriculum. Then, because the curriculum for ALS - SHS is not yet available, they frequently run into problems. In addition, their main problem as ALS mobile teachers is having no separate Learner Information System (LIS) to enroll SHS – ALS learners.

This result is clarified on the study of Karakuş (2019) on curriculum guide. In the said study, it is described as an organized document that explains the pedagogy, goals, and objectives, learning experiences, instructional resources, and evaluations that comprise a specific educational program. This type of document is also known as a curriculum map. In addition to this, it gives an articulation of what students should know and be able to do, which helps teachers understand how students should know and be able to do certain things, and it helps teachers understand how students should know and be able to do certain things. Because it is impossible to educate students without a curriculum, teaching it in senior high school is extremely difficult. However, education cannot occur in the absence of a curriculum.

In addition, Geronimo (2017), lesson plan creation will be far more challenging for teachers who do not have access to a curriculum guide, who are aware that this is the single most significant document in their possession. Lesson plans that are both effective and relevant to the state's aims and objectives can be crafted by educators with the assistance of a curriculum guide (what is intended that student learn). Students gain something from and appreciate well-structured classes, but when there is no curriculum guide, both teachers and students may be negatively affected.

Meanwhile, the Department of Education established the Learners' Information System (LIS), an online registration system for students attending public schools. Since its installation, the LIS has enabled the Department to calculate the overall number of students enrolled in public schools based on real registration data. The LIS is an innovative instrument used by the Department to manage information; without it, it would be difficult to promote transparency, informed decision making, and empowerment at all organizational levels. Without the LIS, it is difficult to realize an inclusive, community-driven process that thrives due to the active engagement and participation of all teachers, principals, planning officers, and other DepEd workers in the Philippines (Llego, 2022).

➤ *Difficulties in Producing Modules and Teaching Materials*

Upon examining the data of this study, one of the lived experiences of ALS mobile teachers is having difficulties in producing modules and teaching materials for the implementation of the ALS – SHS program. Specifically, due to the lack of budget, they encountered difficulties in producing modules for ALS – SHS. Also, due to insufficient printing materials, they had difficulty in producing and distributing more modules for ALS – SHS learners. Moreover, they had difficulty in procuring teaching materials for ALS - SHS because of the lack of a direct contact person who should provide the needed materials.

In relation to this theme, Maffe (2020) stated that the most pressing issue right now is the severe lack of available resources in schools. This issue affects students and teachers, and it has the potential to affect children's parents as well. When classrooms lack resources, both students and teachers may experience extreme anxiety. Students and teachers are not only suffering from emotional anguish as a result of a lack of appropriate resources, but they are also unable to learn to the best of their abilities and investigate potential solutions to this difficult challenge once having a better understanding of the issues at hand.

Conferring to Bottiani et al. (2019), ALS teachers are feeling the pinch as well as formal teachers. Because it is difficult for schools to purchase brand-new computers and printers for all of their students, it is up to individual teachers to devise ways to compensate for a lack of technological resources in their classrooms. That could mean using textbooks if they have enough, or using a projector so that the students can see what the teacher is doing on their screen.

Further, the absence of resources in schools has a significant negative impact on both the students' ability to learn and the teachers' ability to instruct a class. Most pupils benefit more by engaging in hands-on activities in the classroom. If a screen or a module is placed directly in front of a student, that student will have an easier time concentrating on what is being presented to them. If the teachers demonstrate the work for the student using projectors and displays, a significant number of the students will either be unable to see the screen or will be unable to comprehend what is taking place. It is far more convenient to have the screen at a table that is only a few feet away rather than at the board which is across the room. The kids will be able to work at their own pace, and they will have the opportunity to spend additional time focusing on the screen. The teachers are not the ones who are responsible for the computers, but they are the ones who have the impression that they are. They are responsible for dealing with the fallout of not having enough computers and supplies (Johnson et al., 2021).

➤ *Insufficiency of Teachers for ALS – SHS*

One of the most significant lived experiences of ALS mobile teachers is the teacher deficiency for the ALS-SHS program. Due to an excessive number of available teachers who should have been handling subjects, they had difficulties implementing the ALS-SHS program. The absence of co-teachers with expertise in skills training is a further issue that caused issues for ALS mobile teachers. In this regard, they faced difficulties due to a lack of qualified co-teachers who should deliver lessons to ALS - SHS.

When there are not enough teachers, it affects students, teachers, and the public education system. Lack of qualified teachers in the classroom has two effects: it prevents students from learning, and it reduces teachers' effectiveness. Furthermore, a high teacher turnover rate wastes money that could be applied more wisely elsewhere. When there are not enough teachers, it is more challenging to professionalize teaching and establish a solid reputation for it, which adds to the teacher shortage. Additionally, the fact that the shortfall is distributed among students from different socioeconomic backgrounds so unevenly poses a problem for the educational goal.

In relation to this, Edelman (2017) mentioned that the new innovative policy solutions are being implemented across the Philippines to combat the worsening teacher shortage crisis that is expected to reach its peak during this school year. These school districts and state governments are not exactly following the guidelines outlined in the textbook. It is a crisis when it comes to the amount of special education teachers that are available for hire even though there is a lack of teachers in general. For the first time ever, industry experts anticipate that the demand for teachers for grades K-12 in public schools will exceed the supply by more than 100,000. This shortage is partly caused by pervasive low pay and the inability of districts to retain teachers.

Moreover, Eclar (2018) stated that it has been acknowledged by the Department of Education's (DepEd) that there are currently insufficient numbers of senior high school learners in the Philippines to fill the available classes and positions for teachers. The current teacher-to-student ratio of 1:91 in senior high schools is due to a lack of specialized teachers for this level, which requires a graduate teacher to have a specialized degree in a subject such as accountancy, skills, engineering, or mathematics, among other specializations. As a result, there are fewer specialized teachers available. To recruit graduates who, have specialized knowledge, the Department of Education (DepEd) is investigating the prospect of forming cooperation with the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) in the region.

B. Coping Strategies of the ALS Mobile Teachers on the Challenges Encountered in ALS Senior High School Implementation

Just like the implementation of any programs and activities, the ALS-SHS program also encountered various challenges and difficulties. As such, ALS mobile teachers who managed the program faced numerous challenges in sustaining the implementation of the program to provide quality basic education to out-of-school youth and adults. To cope with the numerous challenges in managing the implementation of the ALS-SHS program, ALS mobile teachers employed different strategies to maintain the smooth delivery of the program. The ALS mobile teachers exerted efforts to provide innovative solutions to the problems.

Through careful analysis of research participants' responses in relation to their strategies for overcoming the difficulties encountered in ALS senior high school implementation, four (4) themes emerged: 1) asking and receiving assistance from stakeholders; 2) researching and studying; 3) using other strategies to solve problems; and 4) managing time.

➤ *Asking and Receiving Assistance from Stakeholders*

In this study, ALS mobile teachers manage to deal with the difficulties associated with ALS senior high school implementation by requesting and receiving help from stakeholders. They requested assistance from the ALS supervisor and received technical support from the teachers and principal of the school. Additionally, regarding the necessary modules for ALS - SHS, they requested assistance from the formal system. Then, they also asked for help from the teachers in formal education about the Learner Information System (LIS).

On the other hand, the DepEd helped the ALS mobile teachers by conducting class observations, lab sessions, and individual coaching. More so, ALS mobile teachers tapped the LGU, barangay, DepEd personnel, and NGOs to be the major stakeholders in the implementation of the program. As such, ALS mobile teachers received budgets and printing materials from non-government organizations (NGOs) and barangay officials. Also, to address the needs of the program, ALS mobile teachers coordinated with the stakeholders in the community learning center to ask some help.

Additionally, after connecting with stakeholders, one must develop a solid, long-lasting relationship with them in order to ensure future success. Regardless of who they are, senior or from another organization. Engage stakeholders in conversation and pay attention to what they have to say. Before attempting to persuade others of your point of view, consider their perspective. Effective and open communication is necessary within a company. Keep your relationship based on honesty and truth. Building relationships and establishing rapport with all stakeholders is regarded as being the essence of creating effective, long-term business alliances. If a stakeholder feels that keeping their word will result in them losing respect (Abouzeid, 2019).

Further, Business Mirror (2018) stressed that people with an interest in or concern for the school were referred to as stakeholders. Participants included parents, school officials, the school board, local officials, alumni, and socio-civic organizations that aided in the growth of the school community. Therefore, a positive working relationship between teachers and stakeholders is crucial for everyone to collaborate effectively for the benefit of the students. Students want to receive a good education, and parents want a successful educational system for their kids. This was because neighborhood schools provided future workers, business owners, and civic leaders with training. By preparing students to contribute positively to their communities, a strong educational program strengthened them.

To guarantee relevance and appropriateness, stakeholders must also be central to the process of establishing the priorities and goals of any program or activity initiatives. The development of projects must involve all stakeholders, not just the direct beneficiaries of an initiative. Analysis was done on stakeholders' relative importance. Any projects and programs they are involved in require that they are informed. The success or failure of an initiative can be influenced by the influence and power of a stakeholder. The ability of a stakeholder to influence the implementation of a project because of his or her strength or force is referred to as having power (Lienert, 2019).

➤ *Researching and Studying*

As a result of this study's evaluation, it was discovered that ALS mobile teachers' ability to handle the difficulties associated with implementing the ALS senior high school program was greatly aided by their research and study. To find lessons that were necessary and aligned with ALS-SHS learners, they looked through the contents of the modules. They also focused on the subjects that did not fit with their areas of expertise when studying the ones, they were given. As a result, they focused on learning the concepts and material that required practical application of knowledge. These methods allowed them to guarantee that ALS-SHS students received the proper education.

In line with this theme, Spangler (2022) reported that teachers have a duty to conduct research and study to learn about the curriculum resources and technologies that can connect their students to information and knowledge sources that allow students to explore ideas, gather and synthesize information, and frame and solve problems. Additionally, educators must understand the concept of collaboration, including how to plan student interactions, cooperate with other educators, and collaborate with parents to create supportive environments at both the school and the home.

Similarly, Plotinsky (2022) also noted that for teachers to gain this advanced level of knowledge and create a practice that is distinct from what teachers themselves encountered as students, learning opportunities for them that are more potent than merely reading about new pedagogical ideas and having conversations about them are necessary. The best way for teachers to learn is to combine reading with practice, reflection, collaboration with other educators, close observation of students' work, and discussion of what they see. This type of learning cannot take place in classrooms at institutions of higher education that are cut off from real-world experience or from knowledge of how to do things.

Further, Hammond (2019) suggested that to help students create useful cognitive maps, the capacity to relate ideas to one another, and the capacity to identify errors, teachers must have a thorough and flexible understanding of the material they teach. Understanding the interconnectedness of ideas and their application to daily life is crucial for educators. In order to connect with students, teachers must also be aware of the variations that can arise due to things like culture, family history, personal intelligence, and study techniques. The ability to listen intently, ask thoughtful questions, and carefully consider student work are all necessary skills for teachers.

➤ *Using Other Strategies to Solve Problems*

It was found that ALS mobile teachers used other strategies to solve problems faced in managing the implementation of the Alternative Learning System senior high school program. They ensured to stay positive since they are using their own skills and experiences as a strategy to cope with the challenges. As such, they distributed online digital modules to lessen the problems in printing and in transportation. They also revealed that they used their personal supplies in printing materials. On the other hand, they coped easily with the problem because of getting used to it.

As expounded by Saraswati (2020), a resourceful teacher is one who can locate and use a variety of resources in an efficient manner to offer students opportunities for meaningful learning. Teachers distributed digital courses online in an effort to lessen some of the challenges of printing and shipping. The educators also admitted that when printing materials, they used their own personal supplies. However, since they were accustomed to it, teachers were better able to deal with the situation.

In addition, being a teacher is a requirement for one to qualify as a resilient educator. In spite of the challenges we face, we must never, ever give up. This is both our calling and our obligation. This time also affords us the chance to demonstrate to our children the meaning of the term "resilience." When we, as educators, work side by side with our students to be positive, ensure that learning can still take place even outside of the school, and guide them to achieve all of the learning goals together in a meaningful and engaging way, children may be able to be naturally resilient as a result of us. Children may also be resilient because of the meaningful and engaging ways in which we help them achieve all of their learning goals. To be resilient educators also means to place a high emphasis on professional development and to actively seek out information regarding the most effective methods that can be used to improve teaching (Asiegbu & Okpala, 2020).

Further, teachers who are currently working in similar settings got together to discuss ways in which they may be resourceful despite the challenging working environment. They came up with numerous concepts and ultimately settled on the one where they should make the most use of the environment around them as a teaching tool. Every classroom has a setting that can be mined for topics of conversation, leads for research, and other sources of classroom information. Construct supplemental learning resources using the materials you find around the school. Use to your advantage the communication networks that are already in place (The Open University, 2020).

➤ *Managing Time*

Having time management is one of the strategies employed by ALS mobile teachers to ensure the smooth implementation of the ALS-SHS program. They organized their time to avoid overlapping teaching schedules with co-teachers. Also, they divided their schedule between teaching in ALS – SHS and in performing other ancillary functions. More so, they ensured to manage their time to accommodate regular ALS classes and ALS-SHS. By having time management, they can have a productive team effort.

In addition, setting goals and structuring each day around the most critical responsibilities is an essential first step in managing a teacher's time effectively. Even when something unexpected happens or the amount of work seems overwhelming, instructors can benefit from setting priorities that will help them stay on track throughout the day. When you effectively prioritize, you arrange your workload so that it is dependent not only on the significance of the activities themselves but also on the consequences of their completion. If the results of a project are not as significant as those of other projects, teachers need to be able to determine whether the project can be placed on hold or not (Resilient Educator, 2020).

Moreover, according to Rinkema and Williams (2021), most of us teachers would agree that effective management of one's time is necessary for students to achieve academic achievement in our classrooms. However, we frequently operate under the assumption that it is a skill that cannot be compared to others, and that students either already possess it or should be able to master it on their own. This assumption, at best, results in frustration and misunderstanding, and, at worst, it leads to grading and reporting methods that are erroneous and perhaps dangerous.

Thus, time management refers to a collection of behaviors that enables individuals to do as many critical tasks as they possibly can in the allotted amount of time. Understanding the value of one's time, determining one's goals, organizing one's work, and analyzing one's performance are all components of this process. It is possible that better time management will assist teachers in improving their performance, increasing their capacity for learning, and achieving greater levels of professional success. The secret to obtaining success in one's personal and professional life is to successfully manage one's time, a resource that is shared by all people in the same proportions, and to plan one's activities with adequate care and consideration. Even though successful and efficient time management looks different depending on the kind of work being done, the demand for modern workers to be able to manage their time effectively has increased as the degree of knowledge and skills required of them has grown (Labandelo, 2022).

C. Insights Drawn from The Experiences of Mobile Teachers in the Implementation of ALS Senior High School

In realizing this research study, it is vital to distinguish the understandings and insights of participants about their lived experiences in the implementation of ALS Senior High School. The insights shared by the research participants are a good help to enhance the implementation of ALS-SHS. By careful assessment of the answers of participants in connection to their insights in managing the implementation of ALS Senior High School, five (5) themes were found: 1) positive outlooks of becoming an ALS – SHS mobile teacher; 2) professional growth and personal gains; 3) provision of additional budget, training, and teachers for ALS – SHS Program; 4) continue learning as a teacher in ALS – SHS; 5) assessment and monitoring of the ALS – SHS Program, and 5) designing of specific curriculum for ALS – SHS.

➤ *Positive Outlooks of Becoming an ALS – SHS Mobile Teacher*

Positive outlooks of becoming an ALS – SHS mobile teacher is one of the major insights of ALS mobile teachers in relation to their experiences in managing the ALS-SHS program. It is found that they were experiencing excitement in teaching unfamiliar strands and lessons. Also, they had fulfillment through gaining skills and knowledge as they were able to share it with ALS – SHS learners. More so, they were inspired by co – ALS mobile teachers by seeing the strength of co-teachers. As such, they became more capable and tough in teaching different levels of students. For mobile teachers, believing in one's capability is another way of overcoming the challenges in implementing and in adjusting to the ALS – SHS. On the other hand, they were becoming resourceful in looking for ways to provide materials in the implementation of ALS – SHS. Besides, they became flexible to attain goals in the implementation of ALS – SHS. Notably, they became more helpful and a motivator for learners of ALS – SHS to continue their studies and to achieve their dreams.

In relation to this, knowledge sharing is the process of transferring implicit (undocumented) and explicit (documented) information from one person to another. Knowledge sharing in schools not only boosts overall production but also equips teachers with the tools they need to perform their duties in a way that is both effective and efficient. When teachers have quick and simple access to insights, resources, and knowledge, their job can be more efficient and effective (Starmind, 2020).

Moreover, a resourceful teacher is one who can search out and make effective use of various resources to provide learners with meaningful learning opportunities. To alleviate some of the difficulties associated with printing and transporting, teachers disseminated digital courses online. In addition to this, the educators disclosed that they utilized their own personal supplies while printing materials. On the other hand, teachers had an easier time dealing with the issue since they had become accustomed to it (Saraswati, 2020).

Additionally, according to Brown (2019), it is also possible to codify and make a commitment to knowledge transfer efforts that take place within a school and involve teachers helping and motivating one another. To successfully disseminate information, it is necessary to consider a number of important aspects, including the combination of public bodies and the promotion of cooperative organizational culture in school. A strategy for teachers that is capable of motivating and inspiring individuals to participate in activities related to knowledge management is an appropriate method from the point of view of knowledge management.

➤ *Professional Growth and Personal Gains*

In this study, having professional growth and personal gains is another insight of ALS mobile teachers drawn from their experiences in implementing the ALS-SHS. They were able to grow personally and professionally through studying specific subjects and teaching higher levels of education in ALS – SHS. As such, they were able to equip themselves with new learnings and skills through training. In this light, they were able to amplify their knowledge of the subjects being handled to share added inputs to ALS – SHS learners. Ultimately, they gained TESDA national certificates and other national certificates on specific skills through the implementation of ALS – SHS as an opportunity for promotion.

In line with this theme, according to Goodwin (2017), teachers must have a greater understanding of and mastery over complicated skills. Teachers must have subject-matter expertise. In a technology vocational program, internships and trainings are required. According to the Department of Education, the effectiveness of any educational system is contingent upon the qualifications of its educators. The Constitution's Civil Service Doctrine seeks to improve the quality of basic education. The department hired qualified teachers of junior high school students. The Department Order number 49, series of 2016 - Guidelines on the Hiring of Contractual (Full-time and Part-time) Teachers in Senior High School is of great assistance to certain educators seeking to apply for a teaching position in the Senior High curriculum. Since these students are different from those in the first four years of high school, the teacher must be adequately equipped for the level of learning.

In addition, continuous training, practice, and feedback are essential components of productive professional development, as are sufficient amounts of time and adequate support for follow-up. Successful programs get teachers involved in learning activities that are analogous to the ones they would use with their students, and they also stimulate the growth of learning communities for teachers. There is a rising interest in creating schools as learning organizations and in finding ways for teachers to share their expertise and experience more systematically (Acosta, 2019).

Many teachers receive promotions almost immediately as a direct result of their work on school projects. You can obtain extra years of experience and strengthen your application for promotion by participating in activities like a school bazaar or a school canteen, for example. These kinds of activities are also beneficial to the school. When you have responsibilities such as those of a coordinator or a senior high school teacher, you earn points toward promotion (Barnido, 2021).

D. Provision of Additional Budget, Training, and Teachers for the ALS – SHS Program

Upon analyzing this study, the provision of added budget, training, and teachers for ALS – SHS program is another insight of ALS mobile teachers drawn from their experiences in implementing the ALS-SHS. For them, they must be provided with more budget for the implementation of ALS – SHS, specifically for the equipment and training. As such, they must be provided with more seminars and training to improve the teaching-learning process of the ALS-SHS program. On the other hand, they must be given added compensation and allowance, considering that they are handling multi-grade levels. Ultimately, they shared that there must have a mass hiring of teachers for ALS, specifically those who have specializations aligned with the SHS-ALS program.

In relation to this, the Department of Education (DepEd) is appreciative of the Department of Budget and Management's (DBM) continued support for basic education, particularly the approval of the proposed substantial increase in the Government Assistance and Subsidies programs – Senior High School Voucher and Educational Service Contracting (ESC) – under its Tier 1 budget proposal for fiscal year 2023. Out of the Php 626.18 billion granted for Tier 1 Level to the DepEd by the DBM, as per National Budget Memorandum No. 142, "Budget Call for FY 2023," the SHS VP received Php 39.33 billion, which covers 1,132,155 voucher program beneficiaries (VPBs) for School Year (SY) 2023-2024. Meanwhile, the ESC received an authorized budget of Php 11,05 billion to cover 1,031,193 grantees for SY 2023-2024. With this substantial increase for SHS VP for 2023, DepEd is now better equipped to fulfill its mandate to improve and expand access to quality education for Junior and Senior High Schools under ESC and SHS (DepEd, 2022).

In addition, Tagum City's local government was one of the first in the Davao Region to realign its Special Education Fund by investing Php 27.6 million to support the Learning Continuity Plan of the Tagum City Schools Division of the Department of Education (DepEd). This effort by the LGU in collaboration with the DepEd was a significant boost to the empowerment of both teachers and students. In fact, with money from the SEF, the LGU funded one vehicle for use with the Alternative Learning System and installed P2P Internet Towers in schools located in outlying areas of the city. The Local Government Unit approved the purchase of seven duplicating machines for identified schools, which was supplemented by the donation of 500 thousand pesos worth of bond paper, ink, and other supplies such as flash drives and Wifi modems through the Tagumpay Tabang Eskwela Project CONNECT under the Public Education and Employment Service Office (Philpar 2020).

➤ *Continue Learning as a Teacher in ALS – SHS*

This study discovered that one of the insights provided by ALS mobile teachers in implementing the ALS-SHS was the importance of lifelong learning as a teacher. They must keep on learning new skills that will be shared with learners and for future purposes as a teacher. Also, they must continue gaining more knowledge in teaching ALS-SHS learners. More so, they must ensure to exercise their teaching specialization while teaching a particular strand in ALS – SHS. Then, they must learn continually as an implementer in ALS-SHS for them to be equipped as future-ready educators.

With this, Huyer (2020) reported that the rapid evolution of educational technology, school district policies, and curriculum standards makes it difficult for teachers to stay up with the latest trends and best practices in their profession. Continuous learning transforms teachers into better and more competent educators by enabling them to provide relevant and individualized teaching materials for today's learners. When educators discover new teaching techniques through professional development, they can modify their lecture methods and curricula to better meet the requirements of their students. However, these improvements are often applied gradually, making evaluation difficult. Continuous instructions make their presentations and course evaluations more efficient by exposing them to new delivery methods, evaluation styles, and documentation procedures.

Moreover, according to Barnido (2021), teachers are required to continue acquiring new knowledge and abilities, both for the benefit of their students and for their own professional development in the field of education. In addition, teachers are required to continue expand their knowledge to effectively instruct senior high school students. In addition to this, teachers at senior high schools are obligated to make it a point to make use of their teaching expertise while instructing students in a specific track. The final step for educators to take toward becoming prepared for the classroom of the future is to engage in ongoing professional development as implementers in secondary education.

Further, teachers do not have a structured professional development program available to teachers, which prevents them from gaining new skills to apply across their many different teaching responsibilities. The majority of contemporary K-12 teacher training has been focused on what is known as the "cascade technique," in which instructors first attend a seminar and are then expected to take what they have learned and pass it on to other teachers at their school. Because not all instructors have access to instructional supervision inside a school, it is up to the teachers themselves to select how they will engage in continuous professional development. Because of the significant part that teachers play in the curriculum, it is imperative that adequate training and professional development opportunities be made available to them (De La Fuente, 2020).

➤ *Assessment and Monitoring of the ALS – SHS Program*

Assessment and monitoring of the ALS – SHS program are one of the major insights of the ALS mobile teachers in relation to their experiences in implementing the ALS-SHS. It was found that the needs of the ALS-SHS program must be regularly checked and assessed. Also, there must be supervision of the ALS program to look for ways how to give help so the program may continually grow. Moreover, there must be conducted an evaluation of the alignment of activities of the program implementation of ALS – SHS.

With this, Sopact (2020) stated that monitoring and evaluation is a continuous management function that assesses whether progress is being made in achieving expected results, identifies bottlenecks in implementation, and highlights whether or not an investment plan, program, or project and its activities have any unintended effects (positive or negative). It is necessary to carry out monitoring and evaluation procedures to ascertain whether or not the program satisfies the objectives, outputs, and results that have been established. Monitoring and evaluation assist identify holes and flaws in the program so that adjustments and interventions can be made in a timely manner that are both appropriate and effective in bringing the program back on track.

Moreover, improvement in schools can be achieved by consistent monitoring and assessment, as well as through the implementation of accountability measures. Record keeping and accurate reporting systems are the most effective means of achieving effective monitoring and evaluation. These systems can assist determine whether the available resources at the school are being spent in accordance with the plan. This is also helpful in determining whether the educational approach taken at the school is producing the expected outcomes for the student's education. If a school management team implements the best monitoring and evaluation procedures, then that team will have better means to learn and grow from previous experiences, as well as better means to improve planning and better allocate resources. This allows the institution to be held accountable to the various parties involved (Miller, 2020).

Furthermore, Ferdaus (2018) stated that monitoring and evaluation is a crucial component of all projects and programs since it determines what has been accomplished in the past and where there are gaps to make improvements in the present and the future. Monitoring and assessment play a vital part in many different fields, including education, healthcare, and others. In this article, monitoring and evaluation in elementary education provided by the government are discussed, along with its present practices, issues, and suggestions for improved results.

➤ *Designing of Specific Curriculum for ALS – SHS*

In this study, designing of specific curriculum for ALS – SHS is another generated insight from the experiences of ALS mobile teachers in connection with the implementation of ALS-SHS. They suggested that there must be developed specific curriculum intended for the implementation of ALS – SHS. Also, they expressed that there must be formulated curriculum for ALS – SHS to lessen the difficulties in its implementation and to ease the difficulties that the current curriculum brings to learners.

With this, Karakuş (2019) described curriculum guide as a well-organized document that provides an explanation of the pedagogy, aims and objectives, learning experiences, instructional materials, and evaluations that are included in a particular educational program. This is also called as a curricular map. In addition to this, it provides an articulation of what students should know and be able to do, which assists teachers in understanding how students should know and be able to do certain things. Furthermore, it assists teachers in understanding how students should know and be able to do certain things. Teaching it in senior high school is highly challenging due to the fact that it is hard to educate kids without following a set course of study.

Moreover, the ALS Senior High School Curriculum guide has to be produced by the Department of Education for the benefit of educators who work in the ALS-SHS setting. The ALS-SHS Curriculum guide has, ever since the implementation of ALS SHS, made it possible to advise and provide teachers with the appropriate and correct lessons that a learner must learn and understand. It would be impossible to encourage openness, informed decision making, and empowerment at all levels of the organization if the ALS-SHS Curriculum guide were not an innovative instrument that the Department uses to govern curriculum. It is impossible to create an inclusive, community-driven process that grows due to the active engagement and participation of instructors, students, and schools when one does not have the ALS-SHS Curriculum guide (Llego, 2022).

E. Implications for Administrative Practice

ALS mobile teachers have always been the partners of the Department of Education in delivering quality basic education among out-of-school youths and adults in different communities. As the Department of Education implemented the K-12 program, the Bureau of Alternative Education or the Alternative Learning System expanded its operation by offering learning opportunities for out-of-school youth and adult Filipinos thru the ALS senior high school program. On the other hand, same with other programs and activities implemented by the Department of Education, the ALS senior high school program also faced various difficulties and complications in its operation. As such, ALS mobile teachers who manage the implementation of ALS-SHS have many experiences in relation to the operation of the ALS-SHS program.

In fact, the results of this study highly suggest that the DepEd top management must provide serious action and plan to enhance the implementation of the ALS-SHS program. DepEd officials may explore the experiences shared by the research participants, especially the unavailability of a curriculum guide and LIS intended for ALS – SHS and the lack of teachers for ALS – SHS. As such, the top management may find ways to address the difficulties of ALS mobile teachers in producing modules and teaching materials for the ALS-SHS program. On the other hand, through the shared lived experiences of the participants, other ALS mobile teachers will be able to find suitable solutions to their personal difficulties and adjustments in managing the implementation of the ALS-SHS program.

Another substantial contribution of this research study is to recognize the stakeholders who untiringly support the ALS-SHS. As such, this study would encourage other stakeholders from the government and private sectors to support the implementation of the ALS-SHS program. Further, through this study, other ALS implementers who managed the implementation of ALS-SHS would acquire other strategies that can be employed on the challenges encountered, such as asking for and receiving assistance from stakeholders. Also, ALS implementers could reflect on the importance of using other strategies to solve problems, like having time management to ensure the delivery of work and responsibilities. Thus, ALS implementers would be able to discover that researching and studying is one way of solving the problems they encountered in implementing the ALS-SHS program.

Moreover, this study is of great significance to ALS mobile teachers who also manage the implementation as they could realize that in serving the out-of-school youth and adult Filipinos, they can reap positive outcomes of becoming ALS – SHS Mobile Teachers. As such, they can value their chosen profession as they can professional growth and personal gains while managing the ALS-SHS program. As a result of their efforts, they can be able to help the learners finish their secondary education to proceed to the college level. Besides, through the shared insights of participants, they can reflect that as a teacher in ALS it is important to continue learning especially on learning other specialized subjects as they are teaching multigrade levels.

Furthermore, the insights shared by the research participants could be utilized by the DepEd officials and ALS supervisors to strengthen the program, especially in designing of specific curriculum for ALS – SHS since currently, the ALS mobile teachers are using the SHS curriculum in formal education. As such, DepEd officials and ALS supervisors, as well as school principals, could recognize the importance of conducting an assessment and monitoring the ALS – SHS Program so they to look for ways how to give assistance so the program may continually grow. Hence, through the findings of this study, they can be aware that they must provide provision of additional budget, training, and teachers for the ALS – SHS Program.

F. Recommendation for Future Research

This research aimed to focus on and explore the lived experiences of ALS mobile teachers in managing the implementation of ALS mobile teachers. In this study, there were 10 mobile teachers from the Schools Division of Tagum City, Davao del Norte, who joined in In-depth Interviews and Focus Group Discussions. Upon the examination of the responses of the participants, it was found that ALS mobile teachers have different lived experiences in managing the implementation of the program. Also, ALS mobile teachers utilized different strategies to resolve the problems encountered and to ensure the smooth delivery of the ALS-SHS program. Additionally, this study sought to identify the insights of ALS mobile teachers in managing the implementation of the ALS program.

In relation to this, it is recommended to conduct a further study that focuses on the ALS-SHS program with a bigger number of research participants. It also recommended that future researchers should explore the perspective of other ALS mobile teachers to get broader information or data in relation to the management of the ALS-SHS program. Similarly, future researchers may get the point of view of the ALS supervisors and ALS-SHS learners to get supplementary ideas and findings on the implementation of the ALS-SHS program. As such, future researchers may conduct studies that focus on the other programs implemented by the Department of Education that serves the out of school youth and adults.

Ultimately, it is suggested that future researchers may utilize other research methodologies that can get further findings. Future researchers may apply purely quantitative research or a combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches using the survey forms. Also, future researchers may utilize multiple case studies or case studies to get comprehensive data that would be able to address the gap in the problems of the implementation of the ALS-SHS program.

G. Concluding Remarks

Alternative Learning System provides a lot of opportunities to all out-of-school youth and adult Filipinos. For the past years, there have been a lot of stories of hardships and triumphs shared by accomplished individuals who were graduates of the ALS program. As such, ALS mobile teachers became the key persons that ensure the realization of the goals of ALS, which is to uplift the lives of young and adult Filipinos from different walks of life by providing a second chance to access quality basic education. Moreover, ALS took another challenge in helping the lost, the least and last by offering the ALS-SHS program.

In this research, I utilized a qualitative-phenomenological study that aimed to identify and explore the lived experiences of the 10 participants who are ALS mobile teachers who managed the implementation of the ALS-SHS program in the Division of Tagum City, Davao del Norte. This research undertaking discovered the coping strategies employed by the ALS mobile teachers to the encountered problems by implementing the ALS-SHS. Then, this study identified the different insights of the ALS mobile teachers drawn from their lived experiences in managing the implementation of the ALS-SHS program. In analyzing the responses of the research participants, this research generated essential themes that provided a better and clear understanding of the phenomenon being studied.

From the analyzed data, I concluded that the ALS-SHS program needs a lot of proper from the DepEd top management support since the ALS mobile teachers who implemented the program encountered difficulties and adjustments in teaching ALS – SHS. The top management must give suitable assistance, particularly on a budget to the ALS-SHS program because ALS mobile teachers experienced difficulties in producing modules and teaching materials. In addition, I realized that the top management should provide swift action on the unavailability of the curriculum guide and LIS intended for ALS – SHS. As such, I concluded that there must be the hiring of additional teachers to address the lack of teachers for the ALS – SHS program.

Moreover, as a teacher, I concluded that ALS mobile teachers are undoubtedly passionate and driven professionals as they are willing to conquer the challenges in implementing the ALS-SHS program. I also realized that ALS mobile teachers are very much willing to ask and receive assistance from stakeholders just to ensure the smooth delivery of the ALS-SHS program. On the other hand, I concluded that ALS mobile teachers are always ready to use other strategies to solve problems in the implementation of the program like having time management, as well as researching and studying topics for unspecialized subjects. Thus, I conclude that ALS mobile teachers are championing their duties and responsibilities.

Furthermore, I realized that ALS mobile teachers must continue their untiring service to the ALS-SHS program as they can acquire professional growth and personal gains. As such, I realized that ALS mobile teachers must continue learning new skills and knowledge to be shared to learners. Besides, I concluded that ALS mobile teachers are determined to exert effort in making sure that the program is on the right track so they can achieve positive outcomes of becoming ALS – SHS Mobile Teachers.

Additionally, I realized that DepEd top management must provide provisions for the additional budget, training, and teachers for the ALS – SHS Program. Ultimately, I concluded that there must be constant assessment and monitoring of the ALS – SHS program that can be conducted by school principals, ALS supervisors, and DepEd top management. With that, it would be easy to find the problems and needs of the implementation of the ALS-SHS program.

There were countless instances of doubt about whether this could be completed. There were several factors that were affecting the course of gathering data, such as the participants and even my own schedules, which were both always occupied; maintaining a work-life balance, making sure my family's needs were still attended to despite the bustling days I had, and most of all, the financial challenges I was making strenuous efforts to upend. Despite all of these, I am so much grateful and have not regretted that I persisted and diligently trailed the path of wisdom set by my mentors and my thesis adviser. With constant prayers and the sincere support of the people who witnessed my voyage, the interviews were done accordingly, and the study had reached a logically necessary end.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A

LETTERS OF PERMISSION

St. Mary's College of Tagum, Inc.
Graduate Education Department
TAGUM CITY, DAVAO DEL NORTE, PHILIPPINES
Tel Nos. (084) 216-6205; Telefax: (084)400-3130

June 7, 2022

DR. JOSEPHINE L. FADUL
Schools Division Superintendent
Division of Tagum City
Energy Park, Brgy. Apokon, Tagum City

ENDORSEMENT LETTER

Ma'am:

This is to respectfully endorse to your good office the permission to conduct study of **NERISSA C. VILLABER** with thesis entitled: **MANAGING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL ALTERNATIVE LEARNING SYSTEM (ALS) PROGRAM: PERSPECTIVE OF MOBILE TEACHERS** as partial requirement for the degree; Master of Arts in Education Major in Educational Management of St. Mary's College of Tagum, Inc.

Further, the research title above has been examined by the Research Ethics Committee as full board and has been evaluated to have adequately complied the requirements for the research ethics protocol and is therefore, cleared for implementation using universally accepted scientific procedures and internationally accepted ethical guidelines.

For your perusal and approval. Thank you very much!

Respectfully yours,

PERLA C. PADRO, Ph.D.
Dean of Graduate Education Program

St. Mary's College of Tagum, Inc.
Graduate Education Department
TAGUM CITY, DAVAO DEL NORTE, PHILIPPINES
Tel. Nos. (084) 216-6205; Telefax: (084)400-3130

June 14, 2022

DR. LEILA L. IBITA
EPS-Aral Pan/ALS Focal
DepEd Division of Tagum City
Epark, Brgy. Apokon, Tagum City

Maam:

Good day!

I would like to ask permission to allow me to conduct an in-depth interview and focus group discussion to the selected ten (10) Mobile Teachers of Alternative Learning System (ALS) This is in view of my thesis entitled, "**MANAGING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL ALTERNATIVE LEARNING SYSTEM (ALS) PROGRAM: PERSPECTIVE OF MOBILE TEACHERS**".

The study would be arranged at a time convenient to your schedule. Participation in the study is entirely voluntary all the information provided will be kept in utmost confidentiality and will be used only for academic purposes.

Your approval to conduct this study will be greatly appreciated. Thank you in advance for your interest and assistance with this study.

Attached herewith is the letter of permission to conduct in-depth-interview from Division Office signed by the Schools Division Superintendent.

Respectfully yours,

NERISSA C. VILLABER
*Master of Arts in Education major in Educational Management
Researcher*

Noted:

MERVIN SALMON, Ph.D.
Thesis Adviser

approved:

4/20/22
LEILA L. IBITA, EdD.
Education Program Supervisor

Republic of the Philippines
Department of Education
REGION XI
SCHOOLS DIVISION OF TAGUM CITY

June 9, 2022

NERISSA C. VILLABER
Researcher
St. Mary's College of Tagum, Inc.
Graduate Education Department
Tagum City

Dear Ms. Villaber,

This is in response to your letter received by this office, requesting permission to conduct an in-depth interview and focus group discussion to the selected ten (10) Mobile Teaches, this Division and to gather data for your thesis entitled **"MANAGING IMPLEMENTATION OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL ALTERNATIVE LEARNING SYSTEM (ALS) PROGRAM: PERSPECTIVE OF MOBILE TEACHERS"**.

It is informed that this Office interposes no objection to your request provided that the following requirements are properly complied with, to wit:

1. The endeavor shall be consulted with the School Head of the school where you intend to conduct your study at least two weeks ahead to ensure that no classes/activities will be disrupted; and
2. No instructional time shall be utilized for the purpose.

It is advised that a **copy of the research study in its final form** shall be submitted to the **SGOD Division - Planning and Research Unit** upon completion.

Very truly yours,

DR. JOSEPHINE L. FADUL
Schools Division Superintendent

JLF/SGOD/Research&Planning

Address: Energy Park, Apokon, Tagum City, 8100
Telephone No.: (084) 216-3504
Email: tagum.city@deped.gov.ph
Website: deped.tagumcity.gov.ph

APPENDIX B**INFORMED CONSENT FORMS****ST. MARY'S COLLEGE OF TAGUM, INC**

OFFICE OF THE RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEE
National Highway, Tagum City, 8100 Davao del Norte, Philippines
Email Address: smctirec@smctagum.edu.ph

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INFORMED CONSENT FORM**PARTICIPATION INFORMATION SHEET****DEAR PARTICIPANT/S:**

I, **NERISSA C. VILLABER**, a graduate school student of St. Mary's College of Tagum, Inc. taking up Master of Arts in Education major in Educational Management. I am currently conducting my research study entitled "MANAGING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL ALTERNATIVE LEARNING SYSTEM (ALS) PROGRAM: PERSPECTIVE OF MOBILE TEACHERS".

I am asking for your written and duly signed informed consent to this research study. The purpose of your participation in this research study is to help the principal investigator in exploring the management perspectives of the mobile teachers in the implementation of ALS – Senior High School in the Division of Tagum City. Also, the aim of this study is to discover the lived experiences, coping mechanisms and the insights of mobile teachers in the implementation of ALS – Senior High School in the Division of Tagum City. In this study, there will be ten (10) participants who are mobile teachers. You are chosen as one of the participants in this research study based on the following criteria: a) you must be designated as ALS mobile teacher in the Division of Tagum City; (b) you must be assigned to manage the implementation of ALS senior high school program (3) you must be a mobile teacher for at least three (3) years in the service.

Please feel free to read the following information carefully and feel free to ask the above-named principal investigator if there is anything that is not clear to you or if you need more information and guidance. You must be eighteen (18) years of age or older to participate in this research study.

SIGNATORY AND WITNESS/PROXY CONTENT

There is nobody except you who is required to sign the consent form to signify your participation in the research study. However, if you are unable to read and/or write, you may select somebody to accompany you during the reading and explanation of the informed consent form and sign the same on your behalf.

No witness is required for the consent form to be binding nor is proxy content allowed. But if you are below 18 years of age, parental informed consent from your parent or legally authorized representative and your informed assent are needed before you can fully participate in this research study.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The primary purpose of this phenomenological study is to discover and understand the lived experiences of the ten (10) mobile teachers in managing the implementation of ALS – Senior High School in the Division of Tagum City. This study will identify the challenges of the mobile teachers in managing the implementation of ALS – Senior High School. Also, this study will explore the coping strategies of mobile teachers on the challenges they encountered in managing

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the implementation of ALS – Senior High School. Similarly, this study will recognize the insights of the mobile teachers in managing the implementation of ALS – Senior High School that can be shared with others.

This study may be of great significance to the mobile teachers in ALS senior high school, ALS learners, DepEd Officials, and for future and other researchers. For mobile teachers in ALS senior high school, this study would be an excellent opportunity to capacitate their management abilities to manage the implementation of Alternative Learning System – Senior High School and implementation of other ALS programs. Also, this study would be an outstanding opportunity for them to participate in more collaborative endeavors to realize their ALS senior high school implementation plans. For the ALS learners, as the immediate beneficiaries of the implementation of ALS senior high school, this study will give them an idea of the underlying challenges that their mobile teachers are experiencing in terms of the implementation of the ALS senior high school program. With that, they would be able to support the success of the implementation of ALS senior high school. For the DepEd Officials, this study will serve as the source for looking into involvement plans, programs, and training that would improve mobile teachers' strategic plans to implement the ALS senior high school program fully. Also, the Department of Education officials can prioritize the needs and problems of mobile teachers in the implementation of the ALS senior high school program. Lastly, for future and other researchers, this study would serve as a valid reference for their associated study for future research. This study would help them create additional academic studies on different problems of the Alternative Learning System.

RESEARCH STUDY PROCEDURES

Prior to the conduct of this study, I submit my protocol to the Research Ethics Committee. If you agree to participate in this research study, the following will occur: Upon gathering the data, procedures will be utilized such as, I am responsible for securing an endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School to conduct the study, which will then be followed by asking permission from the Division Office of Tagum City, Department of Education. I am also in charge of selecting my research participants through purposive sampling. It will be based on the set pre-inclusion criteria. I am also committed to protecting the confidentiality of my participants' identities. After which, an In-depth interview will be conducted. The interview for both IDI and FGD should take around 45 to 60 minutes. Next, recorded interviews will be stored in the computer for transcription. Thematic analysis will follow. After the transcription and recording of the data, you will be allowed to review and check to verify if the responses are true and accurate. Further, since face-to-face is not allowed this time due to the pandemic, I will utilize different platforms such as Google Meet or Zoom Teleconference. Lastly, with the help of the expert, the analyzed data will be checked. Should you have questions and clarifications during the explanation, the investigator is willing to accommodate and elucidate to you the issue's concern. You are also requested to read the informed consent.

VOLUNTARY PARTICIPATION AND ALTERNATIVE OPTIONS

Your decision whether or not to participate in this research study is completely voluntary. Rest assured that I will not coerce you to participate in this study. As a human being, you have the freedom to exercise your rights. It is up to you whether or not you decide to participate. If you decide to participate, you will be required to sign this informed consent form. After you sign this consent form, you can still withdraw your consent and discontinue participation at any time

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and without giving a reason. In the event that you withdraw from the study before data collection is completed, rest assured that your data be destroyed in a manner prescribed by law.

RISKS, BENEFITS, REMUNERATION, AND REIMBURSEMENTS

There are no known risks in participating in this study. There are minimal direct benefits that can be derived from this study. There is the extent of benefits and risks of participating in the study. As part of your consent when you voluntarily accepted the request without coercion, you have the option to withdraw the participation in the study at any time. Furthermore, I will ensure the confidentiality of your personal data by assigning you code names, and the data collected from you will be kept in the strictest confidence. Aside from that, I will be giving a simple token of gratitude. It will serve as reimbursement for the time and effort that you will be extending in this study.

On the other hand, I will ensure that you have the opportunity to double-check the findings. With this process, I can guarantee the credibility of the study since I will allow you to check the veracity of the findings. Following that, I will request you to sign up for certification, stating that you have examined and acknowledged the results, which will be shared during the virtual interviews. Additionally, this will confirm the legitimacy of the data which approves that all the findings are your personal experiences.

PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR'S RESPONSIBILITY DURING ADVERSE SITUATIONS

This data gathering of the study will be done from March to May 2022. This qualitative study will be limited to the perspectives of mobile teachers in managing the implementation of ALS – Senior High School in the Division of Tagum City.

The data of this study will be limited only to the challenges and experiences of the participants' taken representations of the mobile teachers who manage the implementation of ALS – Senior High School in the Division of Tagum City.

Further, this study will be confined only to the results of the virtual interview of ten (10) mobile teachers. As advised by the IATF that face-to-face interview is limited or not allowed due to the threat of the COVID-19 pandemic. A virtual interview or video interview is a platform that utilizes video technology to allow the discussion to take place distantly.

Moreover, to avoid the occurrence of any potential type of harm (i.e., psychological, emotional, or social) during the conduct of this research study, I will provide you in advance with information on counseling matters or services or appropriate support bodies (if necessary) dealing with the issue. But in the event that interaction with you may inadvertently harm you in some unintended way, I will take responsibility to address the issue.

PRIVACY AND CONFIDENTIALITY

Your privacy is of paramount importance, and thus, it must be protected by conducting the research in a private setting and/or other space consideration or security measures will be properly observed for online research/survey platforms. Importantly, I will ask you for personal information (e.g., name, age, sex, etc.) or sensitive personal information that could help my

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research or could help me to further understand your experiences. However, I will not force you to reveal any personal information that you do not wish to reveal.

I will make sure that participants who are part of the LGBTQIA community will be given equal treatment. I will ensure to provide privacy if they request not to reveal their identity. During the interview, I will ensure that they will be comfortable. At the same time, I will make sure that they can share their experiences freely. Also, I will be fair and sensitive to them during the interview.

Rest assured that the data or information you provide will be treated with complete anonymity and utmost confidentiality by means of discrete coding. I will assure you that there will be no possibility that information shared in the Focused-Group Discussion (FGD) is disclosed outside of the group. I will ensure that any unauthorized or unwarranted disclosure of research data obtained during FGD shall be dealt with accordingly.

Also, the Research Ethics Committee and other regulatory bodies will be given direct access to the information and data of the participants for the purposes of verification and validation of the procedures and data.

No individual identities will be used in any reports, presentations, or publications resulting from the research study. I will protect any confidentiality of your recorded audio, video, or photographic records so that no one can identify your voice, through voice analysis (audio and video) or physical characteristics (video or photographic images) – especially those obtained during the online orientation conducted (e.g., screenshots, etc.).

All research data or information will be always kept in locked files (for material copies) or password-protected folders (for electronic copies). Only the principal investigator will have access to the files. After the research study will be completed, the data collected will be retained for three (3) years and be destroyed immediately thereafter in a secure manner that would prevent unauthorized access, use, or disclosure to any other party or the public or in a manner prescribed by law.

STUDY-RELATED INJURIES

There are no related injuries in this study. However, I will utilize virtual interviews with the use of Zoom Teleconference and Google Meet software applications. On the other hand, as a researcher, I shall strictly adhere to the safety protocols against the outbreak of COVID-19.

INFORMATION AND STUDY RESULTS

You may have access to your own data. After the analysis of all the data for this research, if you wish to be informed, I will also make the results available to you.

USE OF RESEARCH DATA

The data collected from this research study will be used solely for the attainment of the intended purposes. It may be presented at any research fora and/or published in journals or used

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for any other legitimate purposes, which St. Mary's College of Tagum considers proper in the interest of education, knowledge, or research.

AUTHORSHIP

I am the principal author of this study and my thesis adviser, Dr. Mervin G. Salmon, is the corresponding author for purposes of paper presentation in a public/scientific forum and publication in a peer-reviewed journal. I also declare that there are no ghost and gift authors in this study.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

I declare no conflict of interest.

PUBLICATION

Results of the study may be submitted for publication. The study may be presented in a scientific forum or published in a journal, but in a manner where your personal identity will not be revealed.

CONTACT INFORMATION

If you have questions about the study, please feel free to contact the above-named principal investigator by calling 09976304492 or thru his email at nerissavillaber@gmail.com. You can also contact the Chairperson of the SMCT Research Ethics Committee, Dr. Maria Lalaine P. Chieng at smcti.rec2020@gmail.com with any questions about your rights as a research participant or any related research concerns or contact the Data Privacy Officer, Mr. Erwin L. Sabornido at 09324858115 or email him at erwinsabornido@smctagum.edu.ph for concerns regarding your data privacy rights.

Thank you very much!

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CERTIFICATE OF CONSENT

I have read and understood the provided information, or it has been read to me. I have had given the opportunity to ask questions about it and any questions I have been asked have been answered to my satisfaction. I understand that I will be given a copy of this form, and the researcher will keep another copy on file. I hereby consent voluntarily to be a participant in this study.

Please check the option that applies to you before affixing your signature below with the following options:

- I give permission for my In-Depth/Focus Group Discussion Interview to be audio or video taped.
- I do not give permission for my In-Depth/Focus Group Discussion Interview to be audio or video taped.

For face-to-face conduct of research:

- I have been informed about the risk of exposure to COVID-19 in this research study. I understand that regardless of any precautions taken, [redacted] the virus still exists.

Printed Name of the Participant : [redacted]
 Signature of the Participant : [Signature]
 Date & Place : 6-21-22

This portion is applicable only to participant/s who is/are illiterate:

I have witnessed the accurate reading of the consent form to the potential participant, and the individual has had the opportunity to ask questions, I confirm that the individual has given consent freely and voluntarily.

Thumb Print of the Participant

Printed Name of the Witness : _____
 Signature of the Witness : _____
 Date & Place : _____

Note: A literate witness must sign on behalf of the illiterate participant (if possible, he/she should be selected by the participant and should have no connection to the principal investigator/s). Participant/s who is/are illiterate should include their thumbprint as well.

Statement by the Principal Investigator/s Taking Consent

I, the undersigned, certify that to the best of my knowledge, the participant signing this consent form has read the above information sheet fully or it has been read to him or her and that this has been carefully explained to him or her and that he or she clearly understands the nature of the risks and benefits of his or her participation in this study. I confirm that the participant has not been coerced into giving consent, and the consent has been given freely and voluntarily.

A copy of this Informed Consent Form has been provided to the participant.

Printed Name of the Principal Investigator : Nerissa C. Villaber
 Signature of the Principal Investigator : [Signature]
 Date & Place : 6-21-22

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CERTIFICATE OF CONSENT

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- I do not give permission for my In-Depth/Focus Group Discussion Interview to be audio or video taped.

For face-to-face conduct of research:

- I have been informed about the risk of exposure to COVID-19 in this research study. I understand that regardless of any precautions taken, a possible risk of exposure to the virus still exists.

Printed Name of the Participant : _____
 Signature of the Participant : _____
 Date & Place : 6.21.22 _____

This portion is applicable only to participant/s who is/are illiterate:

I have witnessed the accurate reading of the consent form to the potential participant, and the individual has had the opportunity to ask questions, I confirm that the individual has given consent freely and voluntarily.

Thumb Print of the Participant

Printed Name of the Witness : _____
 Signature of the Witness : _____
 Date & Place : _____

Note: A literate witness must sign on behalf of the illiterate participant (if possible, he/she should be selected by the participant and should have no connection to the principal investigator/s). Participant/s who is/are illiterate should include their thumbprint as well.

Statement by the Principal Investigator/s Taking Consent

I, the undersigned, certify that to the best of my knowledge, the participant signing this consent form has read the above information sheet fully or it has been read to him or her and that this has been carefully explained to him or her and that he or she clearly understands the nature of the risks and benefits of his or her participation in this study. I confirm that the participant has not been coerced into giving consent, and the consent has been given freely and voluntarily.

A copy of this Informed Consent Form has been provided to the participant.

Printed Name of the Principal Investigator : Nerissa C. Villaber
 Signature of the Principal Investigator : _____
 Date & Place : 6/26/22 _____

ST. MARY'S COLLEGE OF TAGUM, INC

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CERTIFICATE OF CONSENT

I have read and understood the provided information, or it has been read to me. I have had given the opportunity to ask questions about it and any questions I have been asked have been answered to my satisfaction. I understand that I will be given a copy of this form, and the researcher will keep another copy on file. I hereby consent voluntarily to be a participant in this study.

Please check the option that applies to you before affixing your signature below with the following options:

- I give permission for my In-Depth/Focus Group Discussion Interview to be audio or video taped.
- I do not give permission for my In-Depth/Focus Group Discussion Interview to be audio or video taped.

For face-to-face conduct of research:

- I have been informed about the risk of exposure to COVID-19 in this research study. I understand that regardless of any precautions taken to the virus still exists.

Printed Name of the Participant : _____
 Signature of the Participant : [Signature]
 Date & Place : 6/21/2022

This portion is applicable only to participant/s who is/are illiterate:

I have witnessed the accurate reading of the consent form to the potential participant, and the individual has had the opportunity to ask questions, I confirm that the individual has given consent freely and voluntarily.

Thumb Print of the Participant

Printed Name of the Witness : _____
 Signature of the Witness : _____
 Date & Place : _____

Note: A literate witness must sign on behalf of the illiterate participant (if possible, he/she should be selected by the participant and should have no connection to the principal investigator/s). Participant/s who is/are illiterate should include their thumbprint as well.

Statement by the Principal Investigator/s Taking Consent

I, the undersigned, certify that to the best of my knowledge, the participant signing this consent form has read the above information sheet fully or it has been read to him or her and that this has been carefully explained to him or her and that he or she clearly understands the nature of the risks and benefits of his or her participation in this study. I confirm that the participant has not been coerced into giving consent, and the consent has been given freely and voluntarily.

A copy of this Informed Consent Form has been provided to the participant.

Printed Name of the Principal Investigator : Nerissa C. Villaber
 Signature of the Principal Investigator : [Signature]
 Date & Place : 6/21/22

CERTIFICATE OF CONSENT

I have read and understood the provided information, or it has been read to me. I have had given the opportunity to ask questions about it and any questions I have been asked have been answered to my satisfaction. I understand that I will be given a copy of this form, and the researcher will keep another copy on file. I hereby consent voluntarily to be a participant in this study.

Please check the option that applies to you before affixing your signature below with the following options:

- I give permission for my In-Depth/Focus Group Discussion Interview to be audio or video taped.
- I do not give permission for my In-Depth/Focus Group Discussion Interview to be audio or video taped.

For face-to-face conduct of research:

- I have been informed about the risk of exposure to COVID-19 in this research study. I understand that regardless of any precautions taken, the risk of exposure to the virus still exists.

Printed Name of the Participant : [Redacted]
 Signature of the Participant : [Signature]
 Date & Place : 6-21-2022

This portion is applicable only to participant/s who is/are illiterate:

I have witnessed the accurate reading of the consent form to the potential participant, and the individual has had the opportunity to ask questions, I confirm that the individual has given consent freely and voluntarily.

Thumb Print of the Participant

Printed Name of the Witness : _____
 Signature of the Witness : _____
 Date & Place : _____

Note: A literate witness must sign on behalf of the illiterate participant (if possible, he/she should be selected by the participant and should have no connection to the principal investigator/s). Participant/s who is/are illiterate should include their thumbprint as well.

Statement by the Principal Investigator/s Taking Consent

I, the undersigned, certify that to the best of my knowledge, the participant signing this consent form has read the above information sheet fully or it has been read to him or her and that this has been carefully explained to him or her and that he or she clearly understands the nature of the risks and benefits of his or her participation in this study. I confirm that the participant has not been coerced into giving consent, and the consent has been given freely and voluntarily.

A copy of this Informed Consent Form has been provided to the participant.

Printed Name of the Principal Investigator : Nerissa G. Villaber
 Signature of the Principal Investigator : [Signature]
 Date & Place : 6/21/22

ST. MARY'S COLLEGE OF TAGUM, INC

OFFICE OF THE RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEE
National Highway, Tagum City, 8100 Davao del Norte, Philippines
Email Address: smctirec@smctagum.edu.ph

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CERTIFICATE OF CONSENT

I have read and understood the provided information, or it has been read to me. I have had given the opportunity to ask questions about it and any questions I have been asked have been answered to my satisfaction. I understand that I will be given a copy of this form, and the researcher will keep another copy on file. I hereby consent voluntarily to be a participant in this study.

Please check the option that applies to you before affixing your signature below with the following options:

- I give permission for my In-Depth/Focus Group Discussion Interview to be audio or video taped.
- I do not give permission for my In-Depth/Focus Group Discussion Interview to be audio or video taped.

For face-to-face conduct of research:

- I have been informed about the risk of [REDACTED] research study. I understand that regardless of any precautions taken, a possible risk of exposure to the virus still exists.

Printed Name of the Participant : [REDACTED]
 Signature of the Participant : [Signature]
 Date & Place : JUNE 21, 2022
This portion is applicable only to participant/s who is/are illiterate:

I have witnessed the accurate reading of the consent form to the potential participant, and the individual has had the opportunity to ask questions, I confirm that the individual has given consent freely and voluntarily.

Thumb Print of the Participant

Printed Name of the Witness : _____
 Signature of the Witness : _____
 Date & Place : _____

Note: A literate witness must sign on behalf of the illiterate participant (if possible, he/she should be selected by the participant and should have no connection to the principal investigator/s). Participant/s who is/are illiterate should include their thumbprint as well.

Statement by the Principal Investigator/s Taking Consent

I, the undersigned, certify that to the best of my knowledge, the participant signing this consent form has read the above information sheet fully or it has been read to him or her and that this has been carefully explained to him or her and that he or she clearly understands the nature of the risks and benefits of his or her participation in this study. I confirm that the participant has not been coerced into giving consent, and the consent has been given freely and voluntarily.

A copy of this Informed Consent Form has been provided to the participant.

Printed Name of the Principal Investigator : Nerissa C. Villaber
 Signature of the Principal Investigator : [Signature]
 Date & Place : 6/21/22

APPENDIX C

VALIDATION FORMS

ST. MARY'S COLLEGE OF TAGUM, INC.
 GRADUATE EDUCATION DEPARTMENT
 National Highway, Maguppo East, Tagum City, 8100 Davao del Norte, Philippines
 Email Address: graduateeducation@smctagum.edu.ph
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**VALIDATION SHEET FOR INTERVIEW GUIDE
 (FOR QUALITATIVE RESEARCHES)**

Title of Research: MANAGING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL ALTERNATIVE LEARNING SYSTEM (ALS) PROGRAM: PERSPECTIVE OF MOBILE TEACHERS

Name of Researcher: Nerissa C. Villaber

Rating: Number of Yes Marks

- (/) 10 Very Good
- () 6-7 Fair (maybe upgraded or revised)
- () 8-9 Good
- () 0-5 For revalidation

To the Evaluator: Kindly check the column which fits your evaluation of the item.

Items	Yes	No
Ethics:		
1. Introduction (purpose, confidentiality, duration of the interview, way of conduct) and closing components (additional comments) are provided.	/	
2. Consent form with conformity to ethical standards is included.	/	
Artistry:		
3. Script is included/built in so, interviewer can introduce, guide and conclude the interview in a consistent manner.	/	
4. Questions are appropriate to the study, enhancing the possibility of getting rich and detailed stories, narratives and descriptions.	/	
Rigor:		
5. Questions are open-ended to encourage in-depth responses, avoiding close ended questions which are answerable by "yes" or "no".	/	
6. Questions are stated in the affirmative.	/	
7. Probing questions are provided with clarity and grammatical correctness.	/	
8. Questions are logically ordered asking the highest priority questions first. Follow-up questions were appropriate and adequate.	/	
9. Questions are stated in clear and simple terms.	/	
10. Number of questions can be covered within 60 to 90 minutes of interview, not exceeding five (5) open-ended items (probes excluded) for every research questions, except for special cases.	/	

Copyright: G.P. Gempes, Ed.D. DM

Remarks:

Congratulations! Your questionnaire met the standards. You can proceed to the next level of your study.

Name and Signature of Validator: **GERALDINE B. CANLAS, Ed.D**

Date of Evaluation: March 7, 2022

Educational Qualification: Doctor of Education

ST. MARY'S COLLEGE OF TAGUM, INC.
 GRADUATE EDUCATION DEPARTMENT
 National Highway, Magugpo East, Tagum City, 8100 Davao del Norte, Philippines
 Email Address: graduateeducation@smctagum.edu.ph
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**VALIDATION SHEET FOR INTERVIEW GUIDE
 (FOR QUALITATIVE RESEARCHES)**

Title of Research: MANAGING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL ALTERNATIVE LEARNING SYSTEM (ALS) PROGRAM: PERSPECTIVE OF MOBILE TEACHERS

Name of Researcher: Nerissa C. Villaber

Rating: Number of Yes Marks

- () 10 Very Good
- () 8-9 Good
- () 6-7 Fair (maybe upgraded or revised)
- () 0-5 For revalidation

To the Evaluator: Kindly check the column which fits your evaluation of the item.

Items	Yes	No
Ethics:		
1. Introduction (purpose, confidentiality, duration of the interview, way of conduct) and closing components (additional comments) are provided.	/	
2. Consent form with conformity to ethical standards is included.		/
Artistry:		
3. Script is included/built in so, interviewer can introduce, guide and conclude the interview in a consistent manner.	/	
4. Questions are appropriate to the study, enhancing the possibility of getting rich and detailed stories, narratives and descriptions.	/	
Rigor:		
5. Questions are open-ended to encourage in-depth responses, avoiding close ended questions which are answerable by "yes" or "no".	/	
6. Questions are stated in the affirmative.	/	
7. Probing questions are provided with clarity and grammatical correctness.		/
8. Questions are logically ordered asking the highest priority questions first. Follow-up questions were appropriate and adequate.	/	
9. Questions are stated in clear and simple terms.	/	
10. Number of questions can be covered within 60 to 90 minutes of interview, not exceeding five (5) open-ended items (probes excluded) for every research questions, except for special cases.	/	

Copyright: G.P. Gempes, Ed.D. DM

Remark: Please follow the suggested comments in the Interview Guide. You may start your interview. Good luck and congratulations.

Name and Signature of Validator: MARIA LALAIN P. CHIENG, PhD

Date of Evaluation: March 6, 2022

Educational Qualification: Doctor of Philosophy major in Educational Leadership

ST. MARY'S COLLEGE OF TAGUM, INC.
 GRADUATE EDUCATION DEPARTMENT
 National Highway, ~~Makurao~~ East, Tagum City, 8100 Davao del Norte, Philippines
 Email Address: graduateeducation@smctagum.edu.ph
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**VALIDATION SHEET FOR INTERVIEW GUIDE
 (FOR QUALITATIVE RESEARCHES)**

Title of Research: MANAGING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL ALTERNATIVE LEARNING SYSTEM (ALS) PROGRAM: PERSPECTIVE OF MOBILE TEACHERS

Name of Researcher: Nerissa C. Villaber

Rating: Number of Yes Marks

10 Very Good

6-7 Fair (maybe upgraded or revised)

8-9 Good

0-5 For revalidation

To the Evaluator: Kindly check the column which fits your evaluation of the item.

Items	Yes	No
Ethics:		
1. Introduction (purpose, confidentiality, duration of the interview, way of conduct) and closing components (additional comments) are provided.	/	
2. Consent form with conformity to ethical standards is included.	REC	
Artistry:		
3. Script is included/built in so, interviewer can introduce, guide and conclude the interview in a consistent manner.	/	
4. Questions are appropriate to the study, enhancing the possibility of getting rich and detailed stories, narratives and descriptions.	/	
Rigor:		
5. Questions are open-ended to encourage in-depth responses, avoiding close ended questions which are answerable by "yes" or "no".	/	
6. Questions are stated in the affirmative.	/	
7. Probing questions are provided with clarity and grammatical correctness.	/	
8. Questions are logically ordered asking the highest priority questions first. Follow-up questions were appropriate and adequate.	/	
9. Questions are stated in clear and simple terms.	/	
10. Number of questions can be covered within 60 to 90 minutes of interview, not exceeding five (5) open-ended items (probes excluded) for every research questions, except for special cases.	/	

Copyright: G.P. ~~Gempes~~, Ed.D. DM

Remarks: CONGRATULATIONS!

Name and Signature of Validator: Dr. Celso G. Casamayor, Jr.

Date of Evaluation: February 28, 2022

Educational Qualification: Doctor of Philosophy in Education major in Educational Leadership

APPENDIX D

ETHICS CLEARANCE

	ST. MARY'S COLLEGE OF TAGUM – RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEE	SMCTI-REC_FO_18
	SMCTI-REC Clearance Letter for Implementation	VERSION: 02
		Approval Date: June 11, 2021
		Effective Date: June 11, 2021

This is to certify that the study entitled **MANAGING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL ALTERNATIVE LEARNING SYSTEM (ALS) PROGRAM: PERSPECTIVE OF MOBILE TEACHERS** of **NERISSA C. VILLABER** candidate of Master of Arts in Education major in **EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT** of St. Mary's College of Tagum, Inc. (SMCTI) has been examined by the St. Mary's College of Tagum, Inc. Research Ethics Committee as FULL BOARD for the initial review and has been evaluated to have adequately complied the requirements for the research ethics protocol and is therefore, cleared for conduct of the study using the school's accepted scientific procedures and internationally accepted ethical guidelines.

Given this 6th day of June 2022 at St. Mary's College of Tagum, Inc. Research Ethics Committee Office, Tagum City, Davao del Norte, Philippines.

MARIA LALAIN P. CHIENG, Ph.D.
Chair, Research Ethics Committee

	ST. MARY'S COLLEGE OF TAGUM – RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEE	SMCTI-REC_FO_17
	Approval Form	
	VERSION: 02	
	Approval Date: June 11, 2021	
		Effective Date: June 11, 2021

June 6, 2022

This is to certify that the following protocol and related documents have been granted approval by the SMCTI-REC for implementation.

SMCTI-REC Protocol No.	SMCTI-REC (MAED-EDM) 2022_021-Version 1	Sponsor Protocol No	
Researcher/s	NERISSA C. VILLABER	Sponsor	
Title	<u>MANAGING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL ALTERNATIVE LEARNING SYSTEM (ALS) PROGRAM: PERSPECTIVE OF MOBILE TEACHERS</u>		
Protocol Version No.	1	Version Date	April 18, 2022
ICF Version No.	2	Version Date	April 18, 2022
Other Documents			
Type of Review	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Full Board <input type="checkbox"/> Expedited Meeting Date: <u>May 3, 2022</u>		
Duration of Approval	June 2022- June 2023		
Frequency of Continuing Review			
SMCTI-REC Chair	Signature	Date	
MARIA LALAIN P. CHIENG, Ph.D		June 6, 2022	

Researcher Responsibilities after Approval:

- Submit **protocol amendments** for SMCTI-REC approval before implementing them;
- Submit **negative events** reports to the SMCTI-REC within _____ days;
- Submit **progress report** every _____ months);
- Submit **final report** after completion of protocol procedures at the study site;
- **Report** protocol deviations/violations;
- Comply with all relevant international and national guidelines and regulations;
- Abide by the principles of Good Clinical Practice and ethical research.

Received by:

APPENDIX E

PARTICIPANT'S CERTIFICATION

ST. MARY'S COLLEGE OF TAGUM, INC.
GRADUATE EDUCATION PROGRAM
National Highway, ~~Maguibo~~ East, Tagum City, 8100 Davao del Norte, Philippines
Email Address: graduateeducation@smctagum.edu.ph
Quality Transformative Ignacian Marian Education

CERTIFICATION

To whom it may concern:

This is to certify that the information provided by the participant (whose signature appears below) during the in-depth interview in relation to the study entitled **"MANAGING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL ALTERNATIVE LEARNING SYSTEM (ALS) PROGRAM: PERSPECTIVE OF MOBILE TEACHERS"** conducted by **NERISSA C. VILLABER** of St. Mary's College of Tagum, Inc. has been verified and found properly transcribed.

Given this 30TH day of June, 2022 for whatever purpose/s this may serve.

████████████████████

Signature over Printed Name

PARTICIPANT

ST. MARY'S COLLEGE OF TAGUM, INC.
GRADUATE EDUCATION PROGRAM
National Highway, ~~Tagum~~ East, Tagum City, 8100 Davao del Norte, Philippines
Email Address: graduateeducation@smctagum.edu.ph
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QTIME
Faith • Excellence • Service

CERTIFICATION

To whom it may concern:

This is to certify that the information provided by the participant (whose signature appears below) during the in-depth interview in relation to the study entitled **"MANAGING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL ALTERNATIVE LEARNING SYSTEM (ALS) PROGRAM: PERSPECTIVE OF MOBILE TEACHERS"** conducted by **NERISSA C. VILLABER** of St. Mary's College of Tagum, Inc. has been verified and found properly transcribed.

Given this 30TH day of June, 2022 for whatever purpose/s this may serve.

Signature over Printed Name

PARTICIPANT

ST. MARY'S COLLEGE OF TAGUM, INC.
GRADUATE EDUCATION PROGRAM
National Highway, ~~Maricao~~ East, Tagum City, 8100 Davao del Norte, Philippines
Email Address: graduateeducation@smctagum.edu.ph
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CERTIFICATION

To whom it may concern:

This is to certify that the information provided by the participant (whose signature appears below) during the in-depth interview in relation to the study entitled **“MANAGING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL ALTERNATIVE LEARNING SYSTEM (ALS) PROGRAM: PERSPECTIVE OF MOBILE TEACHERS”** conducted by **NERISSA C. VILLABER** of St. Mary's College of Tagum, Inc. has been verified and found properly transcribed.

Given this 30TH [REDACTED] for the purpose/s this may serve.

Signature over Printed Name

PARTICIPANT

ST. MARY'S COLLEGE OF TAGUM, INC.
GRADUATE EDUCATION PROGRAM
National Highway, ~~Marina~~ East, Tagum City, 8100 Davao del Norte, Philippines
Email Address: graduateeducation@smctagum.edu.ph
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CERTIFICATION

To whom it may concern:

This is to certify that the information provided by the participant (whose signature appears below) during the in-depth interview in relation to the study entitled **"MANAGING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL ALTERNATIVE LEARNING SYSTEM (ALS) PROGRAM: PERSPECTIVE OF MOBILE TEACHERS"** conducted by **NERISSA C. VILLABER** of St. Mary's College of Tagum, Inc. has been verified and found properly transcribed.

Given this 30TH day of June, 2022 for whatever purpose/s this may serve.

[Redacted Name]

Signature over Printed Name

PARTICIPANT

ST. MARY'S COLLEGE OF TAGUM, INC.
GRADUATE EDUCATION PROGRAM
National Highway, ~~Marinao~~ East, Tagum City, 8100 Davao del Norte, Philippines
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CERTIFICATION

To whom it may concern:

This is to certify that the information provided by the participant (whose signature appears below) during the in-depth interview in relation to the study entitled **"MANAGING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL ALTERNATIVE LEARNING SYSTEM (ALS) PROGRAM: PERSPECTIVE OF MOBILE TEACHERS"** conducted by **NERISSA C. VILLABER** of St. Mary's College of Tagum, Inc. has been verified and found properly transcribed.

Given this 30TH day of June, 2022 for whatever purpose/s this may serve.

[Redacted Name]

Signature over Printed Name

PARTICIPANT

APPENDIX F

AUDIT TRAIL

AUDIT TRAIL	
THEMES	ARCHIVAL #
1. What are the lived experiences of mobile teachers managing the implementation of ALS senior high school? to	
Difficulties and Adjustments in Teaching ALS – SHS	FGD- 01 FGD- 05 IDI - 01 IDI- 03 IDI- 02 FGD-02
Unavailability of Curriculum Guide and LIS Intended for ALS – SHS	IDI - 02 FGD- 01 FGD- 03 IDI-01 IDI- 03
Difficulties in Producing Modules and Teaching Materials	IDI - 03 FGD- 05 IDI- 01 IDI- 03 IDI- 02
Lack of Teachers for ALS - SHS	IDI- 02 IDI- 03
2. How Mobile Teachers Cope with the Challenges Encountered in ALS Senior High School Implementation?	
Asking and Receiving Assistance from Stakeholders	FGD-01 IDI- 01 IDI- 02 FGD- 05 FGD- 04 FGD- 03 FGD- 06 IDI- 03 FGD- 02 FGD- 07
Researching and Studying	FGD- 04 FGD- 05 FGD- 01 IDI- 02
Using Other Strategies to Solve Problems	IDI- 02 FGD- 03 FGD- 04 FGD- 01
Having Time Management	FGD- 06 FGD- 02 FGD- 05 FGD- 03
3. What insights can be drawn from the experiences of Mobile Teachers in the implementation of ALS Senior High School?	
Positive Outcomes of Becoming an ALS-SHS Mobile Teacher	IDI- 01 IDI- 02 FGD-01 FGD- 02 IDI- -03 FGD- 06

Professional Growth and Personal Gains	FGD- 01 IDI- 01 FGD- 03 FGD- 04 FGD- 07 FGD- 05 IDI- 02 IDI- 03
Provision of Additional Budget, Trainings, and Teachers for ALS-SHS Program	IDI- 02 FGD- 02 IDI- 01 IDI- 03 FGD- 01
Continue Learning as a Teacher in ALS-SHS Program	IDI- 02 FGD- 07 FGD- 01 IDI- 03
Assessment and Monitoring of the ALS – SHS Program	IDI- 03 IDI- 02 FGD- 04
Designing of Specific Curriculum for ALS- SHS	FGD- 02 IDI- 03 FGD- 04

APPENDIX G

REC ENDORSEMENT FOR FINAL DEFENSE

	ST. MARY'S COLLEGE OF TAGUM – RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEE	SMCTI-REC_FO_19
	SMCTI-REC Clearance Letter For Final Defense	VERSION: 02
		Approval Date: June 11, 2021
		Effective Date: June 11, 2021

This is to certify that the study MANAGING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL ALTERNATIVE LEARNING SYSTEM (ALS) PROGRAM: PERSPECTIVE OF MOBILE TEACHERS of NERISSA C. VILLABER, a candidate of Master of Arts in Education major in EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT of St. Mary's College of Tagum, Inc. (SMCTI), has followed the protocol set by the Research Ethics Committee in adherence to internationally- accepted scientific procedures and ethical guidelines and is therefore, given CLEARANCE for FINAL DEFENSE.

Given this 25th day of November 2022 at St. Mary's College of Tagum, Inc. Research Ethics Committee Office, Tagum City, Davao del Norte, Philippines.

MARIA LALAIN P. CHIENG, Ph.D.
 Chair, Research Ethics Committee

APPENDIX H

CERTIFICATION FROM THE EDITOR

ST. MARY'S COLLEGE OF TAGUM, INC.

GRADUATE EDUCATION PROGRAM
National Highway, Tagum City, 8100 Davao del Norte, Philippines
Email Address: graduateeducationl@smctagum.edu.ph

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EDITOR'S CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that I have reviewed and checked the manuscript titled, **"MANAGING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL ALTERNATIVE LEARNING SYSTEM (ALS) PROGRAM: PERSPECTIVE OF MOBILE TEACHERS,"** of **NERISSA C. VILLABER** for the second semester of School Year 2021-2022.

JINEDETH T. CEMINI, L.P.T., M.A.Ed.
Editor